

**THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF MIGRATION AND
REMITTANCES ON LOCAL COMMUNITIES: A CASE STUDY FROM
TUTI ISLAND, KHARTOUM STATE.**

by

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A THESIS SUBMITTED IN FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT FOR
THE DEGREE OF MASTERS OF ARTS IN GEOGRAPHY

Geography Department
Faculty of Arts
University of Khartoum

1995

DEDICATION

This research is dedicated to the members of my family, particularly my parents for their endless support and encouragement.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Throughout the research period, large number of people have helped me in different ways. Although it is difficult to nominate all of them, yet it is necessary to acknowledge, at least, some of them.

I am deeply indebted to my supervisor Dr. Usama Osman Abdelgadir for his continuous help, guides and valuable remarks and comments during the course of this research. Also thanks should be directed to Prof. M. E. Abusin for his willing to supervise this work when Dr. Usama was absent. The valuable suggestions and ideas he raised are highly appreciated.

Thanks also are due to all people of Tuti who have followed and encouraged this research. But special thanks are directed to my friends EL Siddig Omer EL Siddig, Amir M. Ali Dalil, Mahmoud Ali Mohamed, Ali Hussien and EL Amin A. A/Raheem for their continuous encouragement and moral support. Also Alaa Eldin EL Amin Taha, Refaat Dousougi, EL Hashmi EL Amin, Hamad Zien EL Abdeen and EL Fatih EL Fadil should be thanked for their valuable helps. I have to express my thanks also to Miss Hanadi Zien EL Abdeen, Nada EL Madani, and Nagwa Khalid for their help during the field survey.

My sincere thanks also are due to Dr. EL Hadi Ahmed EL Hadi, Mr. Mohamed Mahmoud Hassan, and Mr. Tarig Abdeen Ibrahim, without their valuable help the field survey would certainly have been impossible.

Warm thanks should be expressed to all migrants return migrants, and households and other persons who have responded to my questionnaire and interviews.

Dr. Mustafa Harbi and Asim Omer EL Siddig also should receive warm thanks for their help and encouragement. But my deepest thanks and sincere debt are due to the members of my family, particularly my parents who have surrounded me with their continuous patience, support and encouragement throughout the different stage of my academic life.

Finally special thanks are due to Mr. Hamid Ahmed Hamid for his careful typing of this manuscript.

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

الخلاصة

أجريت الدراسة بغرض تقييم الآثار الاقتصادية والاجتماعية للهجرة الخارجية والتحويلات النقدية على المجتمعات المحلية وقد اعتمدت الدراسة على مجتمع جزيرة توتى بولاية الخرطوم كمثال للمجتمعات المحلية. وقد جمعت المعلومات لهذا البحث من المصادر الأولية والثانوية حيث تمثلت المصادر الأولية فى المسح الميدانى فى وسط مجتمع المهاجرين وأسره من توتى بالإضافة للمهاجرين العائدين، حيث تم رصد أهم معالم التركيب الاجتماعى، الإقتصادى والديمغرافى لمجتمع المهاجرين بتوتى. وقد أبرزت نتائج المسح الميدانى أن المهاجرين يشكلون نسبة مقدرة من السكان وبصورة أخص من القوى العاملة بجزيرة توتى. كذلك أكد المسح الميدانى على صحة نظرية إنتقائية الهجرة فى توتى من حيث العمر والنوع والتعليم. كذلك أبرزت نتائج الدراسة أن دخل ووفر وتحويلات المهاجر تتأثر إيجابيا بالمستوى التعليمى والمهنى وكذلك بطول فترة الهجرة. وقد اتضح أن نسبة عالية من المهاجرين تحرص على إرسال تحويلات نقدية لأسره فى توتى وأن أكثرية التحويلات تتم على فترات زمنية منتظمة. كذلك أوضحت الدراسة أن التحويلات النقدية تمثل جزءاً مقدراً من دخل أسر المهاجرين وأنها تؤدى لزيادة دخل الأسر بصورة واضحة مما ينجم عنه عدم تساوى فى توزيع الدخل فى مجتمع الجزيرة.

كما أظهرت الدراسة بخصوص إستخدامات التحويلات أن الجزء الأكبر من التحويلات يستخدم لمقابلة إحتياجات الحياة اليومية وتوفير السلع الإستهلاكية للأسر، أما الجزء المتبقى من التحويلات فإنه يصرف على بناء واصلاح المنازل وتعليم الأبناء ثم الإستثمار. وقد أوضحت الدراسة أن أنواع الإستثمارات السائدة فى أوساط المهاجرين تتمثل فى شراء الأراضى، بناء المنازل وإيجارها، العمل فى قطاع النقل والأعمال التجارية الصغيرة. كذلك اتضح أن إمتلاك الأدوات الكهربائية والسلع المعمرة يشكل نسبة عالية فى أوساط أسر المهاجرين.

كذلك أوضحت الدراسة أن نسبة عالية من أسر المهاجرين تعتبر وضعها الإقتصادى أفضل منه قبل الهجرة، كما اتضح أن الإعالة على المهاجرين فى مجتمع توتى تشكل نسبة عالية.

أما على الصعيد الاجتماعى فقد اتضح دور المهاجرين البارز فى زيادة معدلات الزواج فى جزيرة توتى وذلك من خلال دعمهم المتواصل للشباب الراغبين فى الزواج. وعلى الرغم من إنتشار زواج الأقارب فى توتى إلا أن نسبة هذا الزواج تقل قليلاً وسط المهاجرين من توتى. كما اتضح أن غالبية غير المتزوجين من مهاجرى توتى لا يرغبون فى الزواج على طريقة "الكورة" السائدة فى مجتمع جزيرة توتى.

وكذلك أبرزت الدراسة أن التحويلات النقدية وغير النقدية قد أدت لنشوء طبقة إجتماعية جديدة ذات سلوك إستهلاكي مختلف عن ذلك السائد فى مجتمع توتى بما توفر لأسر المهاجرين من رغد العيش وارتفاع مستوى الدخل. ولكن بالرغم من ذلك فممايزال المهاجرون وأسرهـم يحتفظون بعلاقات إجتماعية متينة مع مجتمع جزيرة توتى. وتتمثل هذه العلاقات فى حرص المهاجرين على قضاء الإجازات مع الأهل بالجزيرة وحرصهم كذلك على تبادل الهدايا مع الأهل والأصدقاء فى إجازاتهم وإسهامهم فى المناسبات الإجتماعية التى تحدث فى الجزيرة حتى إذا لم يكونوا فى البلاد، مما يعكس التواصل الإجتماعى وعدم حدوث أى عزلة إجتماعية لهذه الشريحة الإجتماعية الجديدة.

وقد اعتبرت أكثرية عينة الدراسة أن آثار الهجرة الإيجابية على مستوى الأسرة والمجتمع هى الغالبة والواضحة فى مجتمع توتى.

كذلك أوضحت الدراسة أن لمجتمع المهاجرين من توتى قنوات تنظمه وتتمثل أهم هذه القنوات فى جمعيات المهاجرين من أبناء توتى، حيث تعمل هذه الجمعيات بشكل منظم وواضح على تنسيق وإيصال الدعم المرسل من المهاجرين الى مختلف قطاعات المجتمع فى توتى. وقد اتضح أن الدعم المرسل من هذه الجمعيات يعتبر مقدرًا ويلعب دورًا بارزًا فى دعم المرافق العامة فى الجزيرة مثل المساجد وقطاعى الصحة والتعليم وكذلك الأسر الفقيرة ... الخ، مما يساعد مجتمع الجزيرة على تخطى الكثير من الصعاب التى تواجهه وتقف فى طريقه.

ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to assess the socio-economic impacts of migration and remittances on local communities, with special reference to Tuti Island community, Khartoum state. The study was based on both primary and secondary data. The primary ones were collected in a field survey among migrants, return migrants, and migrant's households. The study reviewed the major characteristics of migrants' community. It was found that migrants constitute a considerable proportion of the island population and labour force. However, the selectivity of migration in terms of sex, age, education is highly supported by the field survey results in Tuti Island. The study revealed that migrants' income, savings, and remittances are influenced positively by the level of education, occupation, and duration of migration. Also it was found that the majority of the sample survey send monetary and non-monetary remittances to their families in the island on regular basis. Moreover, it was shown that remittances constitute a considerable proportion of the income of the migrants' households. Also remittances have put very positive impact on the economics of migrant's families. The provision of remittances to migrant's families has resulted in an unequal income distribution among the island community. Furthermore, it was revealed that the major uses made of remittances are the provision of migrant's families with their consumption goods for the daily needs to enhance the family living standards, building and maintenance of houses, purchasing of electrical durable equipment, parents' travel for pilgrimage and Omra. The major investment patterns were found to be land-acquisition, rent out of the newly built houses, transportation, and small scale-commercial business. Also the majority of the sample reported that their economic conditions as better as than those before migration. The study showed that dependency rate on migrants is high among the island community.

Concerning the social impact, the study showed that migrants have put a positive impact on marriage rate in the island through their support of marriage ceremonial celebrations. Also the study revealed that marriage to first-cousin spouses is less among migrants than the rest of the community. The majority

of unmarried migrants reported that they do not plan to get married according to *Kora* marriage system, the most common marriage system in the island. The study also indicated that remittances have created a new social strata in the island in terms of luxurious life, and patterns of consumption but it was also indicated that this new social strata has maintain very strong social ties with the island community. The majority of migrants are keen to spend their annual vacation in Sudan, and to provide their friends and relatives with gifts. Moreover, most of the sample survey believed that migration has put positive impact on the island community. The study also showed that migrants from Tuti island have their well-organized community at destinations, and they used to channel and coordinate their support to the island via the migrants organizations. Their support is directed to the public utilities in the island e.g. mosques, health, and education sectors, poor families, ... etc. Also the study showed that this support is highly appreciated by the island's local community.

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CHAPTER ONE
THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

CHAPTER ONE

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

1. 1 Research Problem

Migration has become a very hot issue at the global level. Being a growing phenomenon, migration nowadays receives much more attention from different disciplines, scholars, planners and decision-makers.

As a human movement, migration has broadly been defined by different disciplines. It has been agreed that migration is a permanent or semi-permanent change of residence of an individual or group of people (Johnston, 1981). Migration together with fertility and mortality constitutes the major factors that shape the growth and structure of population. Furthermore, migration is considered essential to any socio-economic development process. It is evident that migration is not confined to certain regions, rather it is a worldwide phenomenon.

However, the role and impact of migration in the process of socio-economic development in the less-developed countries has sparked a continuous debate among researchers and scholars. The major question in this debate addresses the costs and benefits of migration. Particular attention is paid to the monetary remittances. There are two distinct view points concerning the impact of migration and remittances. The first view point argues that, remittances are beneficial to the sending areas in the sense that, as migration is mainly based on cost-benefit calculations, migrants move from low to high income countries, and it is expected

that higher income can be gained. This higher income and its consequent remittances contribute to enhance the basic needs for migrants and their dependents, and to improve the standard of living of the families at the sending communities. Also migration and remittances tend to reduce both inequality and inefficiency. They improve income distribution and reduce the relative gap between the bottom and the top income groups. Remittances may add to productive investment for the development and diversification of income generating activities in the sending areas (Oberai and Singh, 1980; Griffin, 1976). On the other hand, the opposite view points raise some doubts with regard to the net benefit of migration and remittances. Remittances are considered too small, insufficient and insignificant to contribute to the local development. This is mainly because very little of the remittances are used directly as a productive investment, while the bulk of the remittances is used for consumption. As migration is a selective phenomenon, it results in a critical shortage of professionals, and trained and skilled labour force, which produces imbalances as far as the human power is concerned. This view point argues that remittances are unlikely to do much to reduce poverty in local community, as most of the recipients of remittances are better-off, hence at the local level, inequality is likely to increase rather than to decrease. It is also argued that, migration and remittances may erode the indigenous work habits, since they tend to increase resources without the need to increase productivity (Rempel and Lobdell, 1977; Hart, 1971).

Among the population of Tuti Island, Khartoum, it is found that migrants constitute a remarkable proportion of the total population. From the field survey it is found that migrants constitute 4.5 percent of the total population, and about 14 percent of the labour force of the island.

Having in mind these figures, this study attempts to assess the impact of migration on the socio-economic aspects of life in Tuti Island and weigh the contribution of migrants to the island local development. Specifically, this study attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What are the major socio-demographic characteristics of migrants from Tuti Island, and do these characteristics represent the local community of the island?
2. Whether remittances are used in productive investment to increase family income or used for luxurious consumption?
3. Do remittances tend to increase or decrease income distribution in Tuti Island community, and do remittances play any role in the income and social equality and social stratification?
4. What is the impact of migration and remittances on marriage pattern and family formation?
5. Whether migrants contribute to the social development and public utilities support in their home community?

1.2 Research Justification and Objectives:

Although migration from Sudan constitutes a relatively small proportion, about 2 percent of the total population, and 5 percent of the labour force, it is argued that this small proportion of population has put some noticeable impact on the Sudan's national economy. Consequently various research projects have been conducted to assess the impact of migration on the economy. However, most of the migration works have concentrated on the impact of migration on the macro level, i.e. revolving on themes like the provision of foreign currency to the Sudan's

economy; the consequences of migration on the national labour market; the impact on the investment rate in the national economy, the governmental policies to attract the migrants' remittances, ... etc. In other words, migration research has neglected the other themes, i.e. micro level studies.

Therefore, one of the primary objectives of this study is to assess the impact of migration at the micro level, i.e. local community and families. Tuti Island has been selected as study area for the following reasons:

- I. The researcher was born in Tuti Island and he is familiar with the island community, which makes the process of data collection easy.
- II. The migrants' segment is of a remarkable weight, about 14 percent of the labour force in the island.
- III. It seems, from a primary observation, that there are some noticeable impacts put by migration on the socio-economic aspects of life in Tuti island.
- IV. It is the first research work to be done in this theme, i.e. no research work on migration has been done in Tuti Island.

So it is believed that this research will help a lot in the process of the evaluation and assessment of the impact of migration on the Tuti Island community.

Therefore, this research aims to achieve the following objectives:

- I. To assess migration phenomenon in Tuti Island in terms of volume and trends, i.e. to have an idea about migration in the island.
- II. To use the available basic data on migrants from Tuti, to draw and build an analytical profile for migrants, to know the major demographic characteristics of migrants' community of the island.

- III. To examine how migrants from Tuti Island maintain socio-economic links and ties with their island community, i.e. remittances, vacations, presents and gifts.
- IV. To examine the social impact of migration on the island community. The major area of investigation in this concern is marriage institution in the island. The research will try to assess the impact of migration on marriage rate and the ideas of migrants about *Kora* Marriage System the traditional and widely accepted marriage system in the island.
- V. To investigate the impact of migration on the migrants' families in the island. This will be achieved through the assessment of the volume, frequency, and uses made of remittances.
- VI. To evaluate the economic impact of migration on the public activities and utilities in Tuti Island e.g. mosques, health services, education, ... etc.

1.3 Literature Review

1.3.1 Theories of International Migration

In an attempt to answer the question, why people move? various hypotheses have been developed. But at present, there is no single, coherent theory of international migration. Probably the oldest and the best-known theory of international migration is the "pull-push" theory, which suggests that migration, all over the world, is due to socio-economic imbalances and geographic differences between regions (Salas, 1984). Massey *et al* (1993) surveyed the leading contemporary theories of international migration, and listed four major migration theories. The first migration theory is the *Neoclassical Economics of Migration*. However, according to Lewis (1954); Harris and Todaro (1970); and Todaro (1976), in this

model individuals decide to migrate because a cost-benefit calculation leads them to expect a positive net return from movement (cited by Massey, 1993).

The second theory, is the *New Economics of Migration* which is corresponding to the neoclassical model. A key insight of this new theory is that, migration decisions are not made by isolated individual actors, rather by larger units like families and households (Stark and Levhari, 1982; Stark, 1984 Taylor, 1986; Stark, 1991). The major assumption of this model is not to maximize the monetary return, but mainly to minimize risks to household by diversifying income through migration (cited by Massey, 1993).

The third theory is known as the *Dual Labour Market Theory*, which on the other hand, argues that international migration stems from the permanent demand for migrant labour that is inherent to the economic structure of developed nations (Piore, 1979). According to this theory migration is not caused by push factors in sending countries, but by pull factors in receiving countries.

The fourth theory cited by Massey (1993) is the *World Systems Theory* which argues that the international migration is a natural consequence of capitalist market formulation in the developing world (Portes and Walton, 1981; Petras, 1981; Castells, 1989; Morawska, 1990). The flow of labour follows the international flow of goods and capital, but in the opposite direction. According to this theory, international migration is especially likely between past colonial powers and their former colonies. In other words, international migration has little to do with wage rates or employment differentials between countries, it stems from the dynamics of market and the structure of the global economy.

1.3.2 Migration and Remittances

One important set of issues raised by the international migration is the existence of strong ties and linkages between migrants and the persons remaining in home areas. To what extent do migrants retain ties with family, relatives and friends at home area. Among the various types of ties and linkages that exist, particular attention has focused on the monetary remittances sent by the migrant to family and relatives at home.

According to Abdelgadir (1989), one of the most important aspects of migration is the counter flow of remitted money and goods, that characterizes the migration stream. However, various studies have been conducted to investigate the size and frequency of remittances and the factors that effect this frequency. Van Westen and Klute (1986) identified four major factors that influence flow of remittances: the length of stay in destination region; the intention of the migrant to return home; the nature of home ties; and the state of home economy.

In an attempt to answer some of the essential questions concerning migration and remittances Stark and Lucas (1988) developed an argument which views remittances as part of a migrant family's self-enforcing, cooperative, contractual arrangement, i.e. remittances may be seen as one component of a long-term understanding between a migrant and his/her family.

Various studies and surveys were conducted to examine the flow of remittances in different societies. For instance, Johnson and Whitelaw (1974) conducted a survey of African households in Nairobi concerning the income remittances. In this survey about 89 percent responded that they regularly sent some money out of

Nairobi. Out of this study they conclude that urban-rural income transfers represent about a fifth of the urban wage bill in Kenya. Also Adepoju (1974) reported that, about 60 percent of the migrants in Oshugbo (Nigeria) were sending money to their home areas. Of these, 90 percent remitted regularly.

When viewed from the perspective of the migrants' income, the amount of money and resources remitted to sending areas are quite significant. Johnson and Whitelaw (1974) found that about 21 percent of the reported earnings of migrants in Nairobi was remitted home. Moreover, the existence of large monetary flows from migrants to their home is also evident by Griffin (1976) who found that Turkish migrants remit on average 15 percent of the income earned in Europe. Boeder (1977), estimated that a total of \$ 16589000 was remitted from South Africa, Rhodesia, and Zambia to Malawi during the period 1958 - 1967, which account for approximately one percent annually of the national income in Malawi (cited by Rempel and Lobdell, 1977).

After comprehensive literature reviewing, Rempel and Lobdell (1977) reported that, the literature indicates that the volume of migrant remittances varies considerably from one community to another. Also they noticed that, international migration, on whatever context it occurs, appears to generate the largest remittances.

1.3.3 The Use and Impact of Remittances

The investigation of the developmental impact of externally generated cash income requires detailed analysis of the allocation of the remitted money, and clear-vision about the major uses made of the remittances. Van Westen and Klute (1986)

report that the bulk of the remittances sent to Mali is used to guarantee family survival. Additional uses include social spending (ceremonies) and payment of taxes. Productive investment is almost uniquely directed to the purchase of land, housing, and private transport.

In the Caribbean, Rubenstein (1983) found that men initially migrate to remit funds to purchase land, or to build, repair or furnish a house as a precondition for marriage. Additional post-marital trips are made to acquire capital to be invested in traditional local enterprises such as shops, sloops, schooners, land and livestock. In their survey of the available literature on the uses made of remittances, Rempel and Lobdell (1977) list, in order of importance, four priorities that appear to govern rural use of remittances. These priorities are: (i) pay off debts and provide education for sons; (ii) purchase of consumption goods to meet every day needs; (iii) education of younger siblings; and (iv) investment. They estimated that the second priority absorbs about 90 percent of the remittances received.

In 1974 Johnson and Whitelaw found the proportion of Kenyan migrants allocation of money to particular uses as follows: school fees 12 percent; payment of debts 2 percent; maintenance of farms 4 percent; and support of family and friends 82 percent.

In Turkey, where more incentives were provided to invest remittances through cooperatives, Kinay (1972) estimated some two billion Turkish Lira have been invested in agricultural activities by the end of 1972. The type of investments carried out include: building of storage facilities, renewal of fishing equipment, refrigerator plants, a milk pasteurization factory (cited by Rempel and Lobdell,

1977). According to Abdelgadir (1989), it is evident that, urban-rural remittances correlate positively with agricultural expansion. Remittances are an important element to the ability of households to break the financial constraints that inhibit increasing farm output. Also it is found that, the increasing amount of remittances enable some households to expand their holdings, hire labour, and purchase farm inputs to increase their agricultural production (Abdelgadir, 1989).

The discussion of rural investment generated by remittances frequently focuses on the purchase of land or construction of houses. Yet, specially at local village level, there is a scattered evidence of investment of remittances in productive activities. In most cases where rural areas receive substantial remittances, it seems certain that the bulk of these remittances is used and directed to the support of family and relatives, and the purchase of consumption goods to meet every day needs, while very little proportion of those remittances, is used directly as investment for rural development. Regarding the role and impact of remittances on the sending societies, and its contribution to local and national socio-economic development, a serious debate has been going on. Remittance impact studies, however, can broadly be divided into two major groups. The first group views remittances to be substantial and play an important developmental role in rural areas.

Griffin (1976) reports that remittances have an important developmental role in rural areas that they reduce both inefficiency and inequality. Remittances are seen as a key element in the removal of existing constraints to production increase in agriculture. According to Oberai and Singh (1980) remittances may add to productive investment for the development and diversification of agriculture or non-agricultural activities in rural areas. Concerning income distribution, Oberai

and Singh (1980) state that it tends to become more equal when we include remittances, which confirms that the relative effect of remittances is much greater on poor households. Remittances reduce the relative gap between the bottom and the top income groups. They concluded that migration and remittances have positive impact on the rural areas, and recommend that any national migration policy should be based on the acceptance of migration and remittances as essential element in the overall dynamics of economic development.

Adepoju (1974) states that remittances have made it possible for large number of people to benefit from development and growth of urban economy, enjoying higher standards of living without themselves being town dwellers. Furthermore, Abdelgadir (1989) states "it is evident that remittances correlate positively with the agricultural expansion". Remittances, as Abdelgadir argues, are an important element in the ability of households to break the financial constraints that inhibit increasing farm output.

While evaluating the impact of remittances on the English-speaking Caribbean, Rubenstein (1983) states that remittances are also the principal source of hard currency in a large number of the small islands, and that the contribution of remittances to individual households is equally impressive. Stark (1980) argues that, migration and subsequent remittances contribute significantly to family income. By increasing the income of poor households, remittances help reduce overall inequality in the home area. He concludes that migration and remittances appear to facilitate ends which are desirable from both "private" and "social" points of view (Stark, 1980).

Griffin (1976) states that migration of peasants probably reduces inequality, and it is one of several mechanisms that tend to raise the income of the poor. Migration

is likely to improve the distribution of income in rural areas, and accelerate capital formation and technological change on small peasant farms.

The effects of rural-out migration are likely to spread widely through the rural community, and if migration is large enough to produce excess demand for labour, there will be a tendency for wage rates to rise and this will benefit the poor (Griffin, 1976).

According to Stark and Lucas (1988) drought is found to be positively associated with the amount remitted; the worse the drought, the more is remitted. They assume that this may reflect the desire of migrants to alleviate special hardship imposed on the family.

The second group of studies, however, views migration and remittances as detrimental to rural communities. Two major objections are raised with regard to the net benefits of remittances. According to Rempel and Lobdell (1977) the first objection is that remittances are too small to be of significance to rural development, or they are spent by recipients on consumption rather than on productive investment or agricultural innovations. The second objection is that, remittances tend to worsen income distribution and increase inequality in rural areas (Connel and *et al*, cited by Abdelgadir, 1989).

Rempel and Lobdell (1977) reported that, very little of remittances is used directly as investment for socio-economic development and that, remittances should be seen as reflecting primarily the self-interest of the migrant.

When discussing this matter, Trager (1984) cited an argument raised by Lipton (1980) who states that, remittances are unlikely to do much to reduce rural poverty

and that those who receive large remittances are better. Hence at the village level, inequality is likely to increase rather than decrease.

Concerning the contribution of remittances to agricultural production, Stark (1980) believes that, there is no sufficient evidence to suggest that migration and remittances can actually be used to transform agricultural modes of production. On the same issue, Oberai and Singh (1980) believe that, remittances may have negative effect on rural population and production, as they may erode agricultural work habits, since they increase resources without the need to increase productivity, and they may be used for consumption rather than for productive investment.

While treating the issue of remittances and income distribution in Caticugan, the Philippine. Hart (1971) found that remittances were beginning to introduce much wider differentiation among the village social structure as many households in receipt of remittances were relatively prosperous compared with their neighbours.

Abdelgadir (1989) pushes this argument further when he states that, remittances is a private gain for migrants and their households, and a social loss for the rural community. The social loss is manifested in declining agricultural output, decreasing household food self-sufficiency, increasing inequality in income distribution, and intensified social stratification of the rural community.

Rubenstein (1983) attempts to be more fair by mentioning both advantages and disadvantages of remittances when he states that, direct economic aid from overseas relatives raises the standard of living and material quality of life of those left behind at the English-speaking Caribbean. But this is not the same as saying

that rural economic development has taken place or that there has been an increase in local-level income producing activities, employment opportunities, or other type of internal economic expansion.

Concerning migration in Sudan, Rural-Urban migration, and the migration to the large agricultural projects are the dominant types of internal migration in the Sudan (Ahmed, 1988). The 1983 population census shows that 2 million Sudanese changed their residence since birth from one region to another. It is evident that the rate of rural - urban migration has been increasing tremendously, creating many problems for the host towns and for migrants themselves.

International migration, on the other hand, has been a growing phenomenon in Sudan. Saudi Arabia and the Gulf States have been identified as the major pull regions to Sudanese migrants. According to Galal eldin (1994) studies on out migration from Sudan show a wide range of estimations; the most reasonable figure is between 500000 - 750000. In terms of absolute numbers, migrants constitute only 2 percent of the Sudan's labour force (Ali, 1988). The social and economic impacts of Sudanese migrants and their significant role in the community identified them as a leading sector of the Sudanese society regardless of their number and volume.

Concerning the geographical distribution of the Sudanese migrants, Galal eldin (1994) stated that, the main receiving country is Saudi Arabia which accommodates about 71 percent of the migrants, while Libya accommodates 15 percent and the United Arab Emirates (UAE) 6 percent of the Sudanese migrants.

With regard to migrants' characteristics, it has been argued that migration is a selective phenomenon, i.e. migrants do not necessarily represent the same

demographic structure of the local population. Hamed and Ahmed (1988) found that the majority of migrants are young males. The age structure of the Sudanese migrants is found to be the most supportive variable to the hypothesis of migration selectivity. Concerning the other demographic characteristics of the Sudanese migrants, the study of Hamed and Ahmed (1988) revealed that crude fertility rate among migrants is lower than among the non-migrants, also the death rate among migrants is lower than non-migrants, also child mortality rate is very low among migrants compared to the non-migrants. The selectivity of migration is evident not only by the age structure, but also by the level of education. Abdalla and Ahmed (1988) indicated that Sudanese migrants are highly educated. Also it has always been argued that there is a strong association between the level of education and the occupational structure. So it is not surprising to find a large numbers of Sudanese migrants employed as professionals, technicians, and skilled labourers. Galal eldin (1994) concluded that, "one of the most important characteristics of the Sudanese migrants is that, a high percentage of them are educated, trained, relatively young and economically active". Furthermore, Abdalla and Ahmed (1988) believe that, by its selectivity, migration plays a leading role in causing some distortions in age, sex, education, and occupation structure of the Sudan's population.

One other area of interest for researchers is the impact of migration on the Sudan national economy. To assess the costs and benefits of migration, several research works have been conducted (e.g. Galal eldin, 1979, 1985, 1987; 1994; Hassan, 1994; Choucri, 1985; and ILO, 1984, 1987). With regard to the impact of migration on the labour market in Sudan Choucri (1985) stated that the export of labour to the Gulf States has resulted in a critical domestic shortage of professional and other skilled personnel. Choucri (1985) estimated that about 44

percent of the professionals stock were abroad. Also in 1985 it has been estimated that as much as two-thirds of the technical and professional work force of the Sudan were abroad (ILO, 1987). The same study revealed that, the Sudanese migrants have had an average 12 years of work experience before leaving. So this means that the Sudanese human capital out flow is more valuable than it is reflected by the age composition and education level (Galal eldin, 1985).

Most of the migration studies agree that, Sudan has been deprived from the most educated skilled and experienced workers, that is in other circumstances could have served the Sudan's economy well. So one of the most serious impacts of migration on the local labour market is that, as the volume of migration increases, the shortage of professionals, technical, and skilled personnel increases too.

Griffin (1979) argued that, whenever the rate of out migration exceeds the growth rate of the labour force, there will be a tendency for wage rates to rise. In 1985 Choucri expected the domestic wages effects due to migration to become more visible in modern sectors, including agricultural sector, as shortages of labour force become noticeable.

It has been argued that, one of the most important benefits of migration is the flow of the remittances to the labour exporting countries. The money saved by migrants and sent back to their home communities not only raises the standard of living of both migrants and their dependents, but also that these remittances generate local development by providing additional savings and capital formation. Remittances are also supposed to reduce the increasing deficits in the national balance of payment and providing some foreign currencies which are badly needed

in the Sudan (Hassan, 1994). The volume of remittances is associated with the level of education, incomes and savings (Abdalla, 1986).

The migrant survey by Al-Ghoul (1983) pointed out that the average income of migrants is 3408 Saudi Riyals (SR) which equals \$ 1000 and the remitted money is about 20 percent of the monthly income. Abdalla (1986) in his survey of the Sudanese migrants in Saudi Arabia found that the average monthly income is about 2611 SR (\$ 780), and the money remitted to Sudan is 19 percent. Furthermore, Choucri (1985) estimated the average annual income of the Sudanese migrants as \$ 15897, and the potential remittances increased to about 58 percent of the income. While Galal eldin (1987) estimated the annual income of the Sudanese migrants to be \$ 11700, and the potential remittances as much as 57 percent.

Due to this wide range of income and remittances estimates, coupled with the lack of sufficient and reliable data, Galal eldin (1987) estimated the annual income of the Sudanese migrants to be \$ 2925 million, and the potential remittances is 57 percent, but the study revealed that the actual remitted money does not exceed 30 percent of the income. Also Galal eldin found that 80 percent of the remittances are sent through informal channels.

Remittances have received much more attention from the Sudan government, as it has adopted several policies to attract hard currency remittances.

Choucri (1985) argued that, the government history of periodic announcement on hard currency might be perceived by migrants as indicating greater risk and uncertainty in policy, which pushes remittances through the informal channels and let the migrants keep their savings outside the country.

Sudan government has developed a wide variety of incentives to attract these remittances, but, according to Galal eldin (1985), all these policies have failed to fulfill their objectives, as the benefits from these policies have been gained by migrants rather than the national economy.

Concerning the use made of remittances and their impact on Sudan's economy, it is evident that, the effect would vary depending on how and in what proportion remitted earnings are utilized for consumption (essential or luxuries), savings, or productive investment. Hassan (1994) believes that most of the remittances are spent on consumption, especially on luxury imported goods. Thus remittances do not contribute much to alleviating deficits in Sudan's balance of payments.

Al-Ghoul (1983) identified the major areas in which remittances are used in Sudan. He found that some 46 percent of the remittances are used for house-building; 26 percent for business transactions; 13 percent for agricultural works; 7 percent for education abroad; 4 percent for joint projects; 3 percent for purchase of production equipment; and 1 percent for other uses. Abdalla (1986) stated that the majority of migrants spend their savings in three major areas. These areas are house-building; marriage ceremonies; and improving the living standards of the families. More recently, Hassan (1994) argued that the savings of migrants allow some of them to run small business in transportation, restaurants, and urban real-estates. Although most of the migration studies argue that the bulk of remittances is used for consumption and luxury pattern of life, Choucri (1985) stated that, even if the remittances are directed to "consumption", they may contribute to enhancing "basic needs" for migrants and their dependents. However, remittances have altered the consumption patterns and improved the standard of living of thousands

of families. A related effect of remittances is the investment in real-estate as a positive impact on the economy in terms of increased activity in the construction sector. Choucri (1985) concluded that, while some effects of migration are negative for the economy as a whole, the benefits appear to, substantially, outweigh the costs.

1.4 Research Methodology

This study has followed a qualitative descriptive approach, although some quantitative statistical tools were used to analyze the data. The study based on primary as well as secondary data. Secondary data have been obtained from published and unpublished sources such as books, journals, conference proceedings and theses. Statistical records were also obtained from Ministry of Labour, Department of Statistics, Sudanese Working Abroad Bureau, National Population Committee, and Ministry of Planning.

Primary data were collected in a field survey using mainly personal interviews and group discussions. Two sample surveys were carried out for data collection, Household survey, and migrants' survey. For the purpose of selecting the migrants' sample, a migrants census has been carried out to collect the basic information on all migrants from Tuti Island, including age, sex, education, marital status, occupation during and before migration, destination, and date of migration (see appendix no. 1). Then a sample of 73 migrants (15 percent of the total migrants) has been drawn from the migrant census based on a stratified random selection procedures. Based on destination, education and occupation, migrants were randomly selected to represent all strata.

According to the migrants' destination the sample included respondents from Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Oman, and Bahrain and others. Table 1.1 shows the number of respondents from each destination.

Table 1.1: Number of Respondents from Each Destination

Destination	Total number of migrants	Sample	
		No. of respondents	%
Saudi Arabia	255	38	52
UAE	88	13	18
Oman	17	3	4
Bahrain	16	3	4
Others	108	16	22
Total	484	73	100

According to the education level, the sample has been divided into primary, intermediate, secondary, and above secondary level of education. Table 1.2 shows the number of respondents from each educational level.

Table 1.2: Number of Respondents from Each Educational Level

Educational level	Total number of migrants	Sample	
		No. of respondents	%
Primary	120	18	25
Intermediate	186	28	38
Secondary	118	18	25
Above secondary	60	9	12
Total	484	73	100

According to occupation, the sample has been divided into professionals, officials, technicians, skilled labourers, and unskilled labourers. Table 1.3 shows the number of respondents from each occupation.

Table 1.3: Number of Respondents from Each Occupation

Occupation	Total number of migrants	Sample	
		No. of respondents	%
Professionals	28	4	6
Officials	145	21	30
Technicians	44	7	9
Skilled labourers	44	7	9
Unskilled labourers	223	34	46
Total	484	73	100

Also the duration of migration has been considered in the selection of the sample, some of the sample respondent migrated more than ten years before the survey was conducted, others are recently migrated.

All the interviews with migrants in the survey have been conducted during the period July - October 1994, when most of the migrants come home in their annual vacations. A list of all the questions to be asked has been prepared (see appendix no. 2) and the answers were recorded and written in the same form.

A sample of 73 migrant households (15 percent of the total number of the migrant households) also have been selected for interviews. The questions to be answered by the migrant household were also prepared (see appendix no. 3). These households were intended to be the households of the migrants selected in the survey sample. This is mainly done to enable the researcher to compare and contrast answers and information provided by migrants and their households.

In addition to the migrants and household surveys, a sample of 47 return migrants (15 percent of the total number of the return migrants) also has been drawn for interviews. Moreover, a number of key persons in Tuti Island have been included in the survey to provide information on migrants and their contribution to the community development in the island.

As mentioned earlier, this research adopted a qualitative descriptive approach for the evaluation of the impact of migration on the island community.

Consequently, qualitative non-parametric statistical tools such as the mean, frequency distribution, and percentage comparisons were used to analyze the data. Quantitative data is presented and illustrated in different format such as tables, histograms, bar graphs and line graphs.

1.5 Thesis Organization

This thesis is divided into six chapters. Chapter one is devoted to build the theoretical framework of the study. It deals with the research problem, justification, objectives literature review, methodology and the thesis structure. Chapter two is intended to deal with the geographical setting of the study area, i.e. it deals with the Tuti Island community. Chapter three presents the major characteristics of the migrants from Tuti Island in terms of age structure, marital status, destinations, income, remittances, ... etc. Chapter four tackles the economic impacts of migration and remittances on Tuti Island community. Chapter five reviews the social and cultural impacts of migration and remittances on the island's community. The last chapter summarises and concludes the major findings of this study.

CHAPTER TWO

TUTI ISLAND: A GEOGRAPHICAL SETTING

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2.1 Location of Tuti Island

Tuti is a crescent-shaped island. It lies in the heart of the national capital of the Sudan. Khartoum is located at the Southern side of the island, Omdurman at the Western side, while Khartoum North is located at the Eastern side, (Figure 2.1). Tuti is completely surrounded by water, as the Blue Nile flows on the East side and the White Nile on the South and West to the island.

The river bank erosion has a serious effect on the island's shape. In the past, the Eastern part of the island was built into the river in a convex shape, but as a result of the river bank erosion, this part has turned into a concave shape (Ibrahim and AL Burea, 1991).

Abdel Raheem (1975) argued that Tuti Island has been formed as a result of the silt depositions which lies on sedimentary rocks. These rocks are overlaid with clay and silt, and they outcrop in the central part of the island.

The surface of the island is flat, with a gentle slight slope, runs from the North western parts of the island to the South eastern parts of the island. The annual floods frequently submerge the South eastern parts of the island, which indicates that this area is the most lower part of the island (Mohamed, 1989).

Fig(2.1) Location of Tuti Island

Source : Ibrahim and El Burea (1991)

2.2 Population of Tuti Island

Concerning the ethnic structure of the population of Tuti Island, the "Tutian" residents can be considered as one large extended family. They claim to be descendants of the Mahass tribe of the Northern Sudan. It has been argued that, Tuti Mahass had originally migrated to the island since the 15th and 16th centuries (Hill, 1965).

So one noticeable remark is that the ethnic structure in Tuti is very homogenous. Although Tuti population are relatives and descendants of one tribe, one can easily identify several large families (Hill, 1965). These families are exclusively Mahass. In the past they represented the major and the most important social institutions, as nearly all of the life aspects should be examined and reviewed through these institutions. So in other words these families constitute one of the major decision-making channels in Tuti society.

Although Mahass is the predominant ethnic group, Tuti Island accommodates some other minorities of Non-Mahass origins. For instance, one of these minorities is the Kunuz of Egyptian origin. Their arrival to Tuti returned back to several generations. They are now considered as Tutians. Also there are some other ethnic groups, but with a marginal importance and influence upon the ethnic structure of the island. All these ethnic groups are considered as outsiders "strangers". They include Southerners, Westerners - mainly from Darfur, and some Arab tribes. The latter groups had come principally for work, and they have settled in Tuti, with the minimal interaction and assimilation process.

Concerning population size and growth, since 1955 Tuti population has been enumerated several times. As part of the country, Tuti population has been included in the national censuses of 1955, 1973, 1983 and 1993. Moreover, a private enumeration was carried out by Omer Bashir EL Hassan in 1963, while he was doing his B. A. dissertation. Also in 1988 the Khartoum University Students and Graduates Association (KUSGA) made a population and housing census for Tuti Island. Being a part of the National capital of the Sudan, Tuti population was included in the 1991 population survey in Khartoum.

**Table 2.1: Population Size, Growth, and Structure in Tuti Island
1955 - 1993.**

Year	Total	Males		Females		M/F ratio	Increase %
		No.	%	No.	%		
1955	5851	3220	55	2631	45	122.4	-
1963	3939	1966	49.9	1973	50.1	99.6*	-32.7
1973	6515	3576	55	2939	45	121.7	11.3
1983	7133	3795	53	3339	47	113.7	9.5
1988	8429	4670	55	3759	45	124.2	18.2
1991	9416	-	-	-	-	-	11.7
1993	10862	5760	53	5102	47	112.9	13.3

Source: Compiled from the different censuses.

The population of Tuti Island has been continuously growing. With the exception of the 1963 numbers, the general trend is that the population of Tuti is in a growing number. In 1955 the total number was 5851, but the most surprising matter is the great difference between 1963 and 1955 figures. This difference is almost is estimated to be -32.7 percent. As this figure of 1963 was cited by O.B.

EL Hassan as a result of his private enumeration, one expects that, he should make some sort of justification for this record. But actually the discrepancy between the two figures he found difficult to explain or to justify, either in terms of large number of strangers resident in Tuti in 1955, or by any large scale transfers of population. EL Hassan also suggested that the sampling techniques used in 1956 census may partly be responsible for this difference. But for us it still needs much more explanation concerning this large difference.

**Figure 2.2: Population Size, Growth and Structure in Tuti Island
1955 - 1993**

Source: Derived from Table 2.1

One major fact that should be mentioned here is that this 1963 census dealt exclusively with Tutian people, i.e. it concerned with the group that can be called the islanders, and excludes strangers who live and work in Tuti. EL Hassan estimated the number of strangers residing in Tuti as 300, and the number of the permanent residents, temporarily absent, as 100, giving him a total number for the islanders of some 4339.

It has been estimated that the natural increase rates in the Third World range between 2 - 3.5 percent per annum, a rate at which the population can more than double itself within the lifetime of generation, i.e. 25 years (Dickenson, 1983). If we consider the growth between 1955 and 1993, the growth rate is about 1.9 percent per annum, which means a little bit less than being doubled. So one can claim that, with some reservations, the natural increase rate of Tuti population is somewhere around 2 percent. However, this rate is considered ~~as~~ low, compared with the national capital increased rate. The population of the National Capital increased by 4.8 percent and 6.3 percent annually between 1955/1973 and 1973/1983, respectively. Actually these rates are considered as a rapid rates of increase, since all rates above 2 percent are considered high (El- Tay, 1988).

With the exception of 1988 increased rate, the annual rate can be considered as a regular one, as it has been revolving around the average of 12.2 percent. However, the period 1983 - 1988 has witnessed a rapid population growth, as the number of the total population of Tuti Island has increased from 7133 to 8429, i.e. almost 18.2 percent within five-year period.

Compared with the other increased rates, it can be considered as a high rate during such a short period 1983 - 1988. Sudan, as a whole, has experienced a serious and frequent natural disasters. During the same period, namely the 1984 - 1985, Sudan suffered from severe drought and desertification, continuous crop failure, shortage of rainfall ... etc. The most affected areas by these disasters are the remote areas and the traditional agricultural sector of the Sudan. The direct consequence of these problems was the intensive and extensive flow of rural-urban migrants towards the large urban centers, especially the National Capital, i.e. Khartoum. Since migrants or displaced people were seeking mainly work

age structure of a population is very essential for social and economic planning. It can show the potential school population and the potential labour force. Age is also an important variable in the study of mortality, fertility and labour force participation rates.

In 1963 EL Hassan did not attempt to provide us with detailed age and sex structure for Tuti Island. He adopted very broad age groups, as they can be seen in Table 2.2 and Figure 2.3 below. Furthermore, the definition of age-groups or age-boundaries adopted by him were rather vague, for instance, puberty was not clearly defined.

Table 2.2: Population of Tuti Island by Sex and Age (1963)

Population Number	Age groups							
	Under one year		1 - 5 Years		5 - Under puberty		Over puberty	
Total	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
3939	95	2.5	440	11	1203	30.5	2201	56

Source: EL Hassan (1963).

However, it appears from the table that the population of Tuti Island was very young. For instance, about 2.5 percent of the population were under one year of age, about 11 percent of the island population were in the age group 1 to 5 years of age, while about 30.5 percent were between 5 years of age and puberty. However, the total percentage of the population who were aged under the puberty was estimated to be 44 percent of the total population of the island. This high proportion of population under puberty may indicate that the rate of birth was relatively high at that time.

Figure 2.3: Population of Tuti Island by Age Group (1963)

Source: Based on Table 2.2

The 1988 census, on the other hand, provide us with more detailed information about the age structure in Tuti Island. Table 2.3 shows that about 10.4 percent of the total population (874) were under 5 years of age, and some 30 percent of the total population (2532) were under 15 years of age (approximately the age of puberty). Having in mind the percentages attained by the 1963 census, we can compare the age structure of the Tuti population in 1963 with that of 1988. The major fact that we can point out is that, the population of Tuti Island in 1988 was not as young as it was in 1963. The difference between the percentages of the young population (below 15 years of age) in 1963 and 1988, stands as an indicator which provides us with some lights about the birth rate during this period. So it is possible to state that the birth rate during the 1960's was higher than that of the 1980's. This statement is built upon the percentages of the

population under 15 years of age. One of the leading factors to this fact is the number of the married persons in both periods, as it is widely accepted that the higher the percentage of the married persons, the higher the birth rate will be and vice versa. However, EL Hassan (1963) stated that the segment of the married persons formed some 65.5 percent of the total islanders over the age of puberty. While the 1988 census, on the other hand, stated that the married persons constitute 40 percent of the total population over puberty in Tuti Island, the distinct difference in the percentages of the married persons in 1963 and 1988, can be attributed to different factors. Mainly it is highly associated with the social values and traditions concerning marriage in Tuti Island. In 1950's and 1960's the marriage ceremonies and practices were extremely simple, as *Kora* marriage system was adopted by the entire society. *Kora* marriage system is an agreed-upon system designed principally to ease the process of the marriage ceremonies and procedures. Actually this marriage system was originally initiated in Tuti Island, so it was a very strong social system, to the extent that, no one dared to break it. The prevalence of this marriage system has led to a substantial increase in the percentage of the married persons.

During the 1980's, on the other extreme, the intensity of the *Kora* marriage system has highly declined and its influence was restricted. Moreover, during the period of 1980's the economic conditions in the Sudan, as a whole, made it much more difficult for people to get married or to maintain large families. Besides, prior the 1960's the children used to help a lot in the agricultural activities in Tuti Island. Nowadays, the direct economic value of the children is highly restricted, where now they have to be sent to school for education.

With regard to male/female ratio, Table 2.1 shows that male/female ratios in Tuti Island are relatively high compared with the national ratios. Male/female ratios in Tuti Island, with the exception of 1963 ones, are higher than those of the Sudan. For instance, in 1983 and 1993 the male/female ratio in the Sudan is 104.3, and 100.8 male stands for each 100 female, respectively. In Khartoum state, for the same periods, the male/female ratios are 118.3, and 113.5 male stands for each 100 female, respectively. Concerning this ratio in Tuti, we can notice that male/female ratios are coinciding with those ratios of the National Capital. This may be due to the fact that Khartoum is one of the major pull region to the internal migration, which is predominantly by males. From Table 2.1 we can notice that in all these censuses, males outnumbered females. They constitute between 53 - 55 percent of the total population of the island. In the case of 1963 census, where the strangers were excluded, females outnumbered males. The strangers in Tuti Island at that time constituted almost 300 persons, and since they had come to the island looking for work, it would be reasonable that males should constitute the majority among them. So if they had been excluded from the enumeration, this would, definitely, effect the male/female ratio, and this what was exactly and actually happened.

Table 2.3: Population of Tuti Island by Age Groups (1988)

Age groups	Numbers	%
1 - 5	874	10.4
6 - 10	820	9.7
11 - 15	838	9.9
16 - 20	1090	12.9
21 - 25	1054	12.5
26 - 30	950	11.3
31 - 35	647	7.7
36 - 40	545	6.5
41 - 45	408	4.8
46 - 50	340	4.1
51 - 55	273	3.2
56 - 60	212	2.5
60 +	377	4.5
Total	8429	100.00

Source: 1988 census.

2.3 Education in Tuti Island

Historically Tuti Island was known as one of the most ancient and important centers for religious teaching. Since the middle of the 16th century, people from different parts of the Sudan used to migrate towards Tuti Island in order to receive some basic religious education in *Khalwas* (Quranic schools) of Tuti Island (Abu Saleem, 1971). Some prominent holy men had taught people from different parts of the Sudan at various historical periods. Since early days, the

"Quran-fire" had never been faded away. During that time the old mosque of Tuti had been playing a significant role in leading the wheel of education. It functioned as a major religious center for teaching people the principles of Islam, as well as how to read and write.

The formal education, on the other hand, has started in Tuti at the beginning of this century. The first elementary school for boys was opened in 1917 with four teachers at that time (Mohamed, 1989). As a result of the continuous successes of the formal education in Tuti Island, and the promising future of the school leavers, Khalwas' attraction had begun to decrease gradually. By 1947 the role of the Khalwas was extremely marginal in the process of education in Tuti Island (Mohamed, 1989).

In 1946 the Tuti Development Company was established. This company provided the farmers with the pumps for irrigation. Thus the small boys were relieved from the hard agricultural works, and they had been sent to schools instead of farms. The direct result of the establishment of this company is that the education enrollment has increased substantially (Mohamed, 1989).

Although the female formal education was lagging behind that of males', since the late 1940's, a home classroom for girls and women was established and it was supervised by some educated women from the island. In 1952 an elementary school for girls was officially opened. By the beginning of 1970's, the capacity of the primary schools for both girls and boys was doubled. In 1969, an intermediate school for boys was established, followed, in 1975, by an intermediate school for girls. The latest achievement in the field of education institutions in Tuti Island was the establishment of Tuti Higher Secondary School

for Girls, which was opened in 1984. It may worth mentioning that all these institutions were built through the self-help efforts and the government support was generally limited and marginal.

Nowadays the overwhelming majority of Tuti pupils are receiving their education inside the island, except those male pupils of the secondary level and those students of post-secondary education, who receive their education outside the island.

According to EL Hassan (1963) the number of the educated people was about 1783 persons which constitutes about 45.3 percent of the population at the age of education. During the same period the literate people was estimated to be some 2156 persons, i.e. they represent about 54.7 percent of the total population at the age of education. No doubt this ratio of educated people in Tuti Island at that time was a high ratio compared with the national percentage of the illiteracy in the Sudan. The percentage of illiterate people in 1956 was reported to be some 86.0 percent which was very high percentage. However, during the period of the 1970's, some serious, effective and appreciated efforts were exerted to reduce the volume of illiteracy in the island. These efforts have mainly been implemented through establishing evening schools for adult education for both males and females. These efforts, combined with the long history of the formal education services, were crowned with a very fruitful results. In 1988 census results, a marked and substantial change in the illiteracy volume has taken place in the island.

According to the 1988 census results, the total number of the illiterate people in Tuti Island was some 810 persons, i.e. they represented only 11 percent of the

total population at the age of education. According to the National Third Population Census, the percentage of the illiterate people is reported to be some 64 percent. So, it is, no doubt, Tuti Island has got a very marginal percentage of its population who have been identified as illiterate. Not only Tuti has got only 11 percent of the population, but also the percentage of the students among the total population has increased greatly in 1988 as it is reported to be 30 percent compared with only 14.3 percent in 1963. This may indicate that the education in Tuti Island has witnessed a progressive stage during the period 1963 - 1988.

From the distribution of population of Tuti Island by the educational level attained, which is shown in Table 2.4 and Figure 2.4, it is obvious that elementary education is the most widespread, representing some 31.9 percent of the educated people. It is followed by the secondary education which has got some 27.7 percent, then intermediate education with 20.2 percent and higher education with 10.3 percent.

Table 2.4: Distribution of Tuti Population by Level of Education Attained 1988.

Level	Illiterate	Primary	Intermediate	Secondary	Higher	Total
No.	810	2346	1486	1956	759	7357
%	11.0	31.9	20.2	26.6	10.3	100.00

Source: 1988 census.

Having in mind this bright situation of education in Tuti Island, one can describe Tuti Island as "an educated society". The direct result of this high level of education, is that a large segment of the population are holding governmental posts. Although the majority of them hold junior and minor posts such as clerks

and accountants, but still there is a considerable proportion which occupies some senior posts in governmental and non-governmental organizations.

Figure 2.4: Distribution of Tuti Population by Level of Education Attained 1988.

Source: Based on Table 2.4.

2.4 Labour Force in Tuti Island

To measure the labour force, we can either use the approach of the "gainful worker" or the approach of the "active population". In the first approach the enumerator in a survey or a census asks each person about his gainful occupation. In this case, those looking for jobs for the first time will be included in the labour force. Also this approach will include the labour force persons who are no longer actively employed or looking for work such as pensioners and income receipt. This is so because the "gainful work" approach is not restricted to a specific period of time. In other words, it gives no regard as to when the work was exactly done. The approach of the active population includes in the labour force all persons actively working or seeking work during a specific period of time. For instance, the month preceding the enumeration. This

approach tends to exclude those persons with job but not at work in the specific time reference (Galal eldin, 1975: 32).

To measure the labour force in Tuti Island both EL Hassan (1963) and the 1988 census, used the "gainful worker" approach. In 1963, EL Hassan stated that all persons who were gainfully employed, or were actively engaged in economic activities were 1231 persons, or about 29 percent of the total population of Tuti Island. In the 1988 census, on the other hand, the results indicate that the gainfully employed people in Tuti Island are about 2972 persons. In percentage terms, they represented almost 35 percent of the total population of the island.

In other words the labour force participation rate, i.e. the proportion of persons who are classified as being members of the labour force in 1963 and 1988, were 29 percent and 35 percent, respectively. The labour force participation rate for the Sudan in 1973 was reported as 30 percent (Galal eldin, 1975). This rate, however, is considered as a rather low rate for the country as a whole. While dealing with 1963 and 1988 census data, it is found that both censuses have mentioned nothing about the sex and age structure of the labour force in Tuti Island.

According the 1988 census, there are 5457 persons, whose main occupation or activities are not economic, mainly students and household duties. Both students and household have subsidiary economic occupations. Since the students segment can, by way or another, participate in the economic activities, they can be considered as potential labour force. If we add the students segment to the economically active population, the labour force proportion in Tuti Island would then be raised from 35 percent to some 65 percent, which is a large proportion.

As for the distribution of labour force by occupation, we can state that there are no real or big differences between the results of 1963 and 1988 censuses, as far as the distribution of labour force among occupation is concerned. Table 2.5 shows that those who were classified as farmers in 1963 and 1988 censuses were 33 percent and 34 percent, respectively.

Table 2.5: Distribution of the Labour Force by Occupation in Tuti Island 1963 and 1988.

Occupation	Farmers		G. employ.		Workers		Others		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1963	404	33	413	33.5	350	28.5	64	5	1231	100
1988	1024	34	940	31.6	604	20.3	404	13.6	2972	100

Source: 1963 and 1988 censuses.

The results of the two censuses revealed that those who engaged in governmental work, i.e. civil service, constitute 33 percent in 1963 while they represented 31.6 percent in 1988. The percentage of workers who engaged in the manual and physical works, such as construction works, slightly showed a change, as their percentage among the labour force was 28.5 percent in 1963, while the 1988 percentage dropped to 20.3 percent of the labour force. This may be due to the high percentage of educated people in Tuti Island. It is agreed upon that, the educated people tend to refuse the hard and manual works.

In contrast, the number of the people who have been included in the category of "others" has markedly increased, as their percentage in 1963 was only 5 percent, and in 1988 it changed sharply to become 13.6 percent, i.e. more than double. Having in mind the increase of the educated people, this should automatically be

reflected upon the number of persons involved in the governmental works. However, since this category holds a stagnant percentage, it is more acceptable that the category of "others" has absorbed the increase of the educated people. During the last decade, however, the attraction of the civil service is no longer strong or sufficient to pull the educated people, since this type of occupation does not respond to employee's basic needs and aspirations. This mainly because the financial return for the civil servant can hardly make him survive.

Figure 2.5: Distribution of Labour Force by Occupation in Tuti Island 1963, 1988.

Source: Based on Table 2.5.

As a result of this unsatisfactory conditions, large number of people tend to leave civil service sector and seek for any other alternative by which one can increase his income. Large group of school leavers involved into some small commercial business, which looks much more attractive than the civil service sector. Also one major factor that may lead to this marked change in 1988 results, may be a methodological one, i.e. it is possible that the way in which the questionnaires were designed had led to these results. In other terms, the questionnaire may

include a very restricted and limited definition for the occupations, as it is possible that no enough alternatives have been provided.

CHAPTER THREE

CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANTS FROM TUTI ISLAND

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CHARACTERISTICS OF MIGRANTS FROM TUTI ISLAND

3.1 Introduction

The main objective of this study is to assess the socio-economic impacts of migration on Tuti Island community. To have a good idea about the impact of migration, some attention should be directed to the migrants themselves. This chapter tries to review the major characteristics of migrants from Tuti Island. It reviews the volume and trend of migration from Tuti Island. Also it reviews the age and sex structure of migrants' and the educational level attained by migrants from Tuti. The economic activities practiced by the migrant before and during migration period is also examined in this chapter. Moreover, this chapter examines the level of income and savings among migrants, and consequently the volume of remittances sent back by migrants to their families in Tuti Island.

3.2 Volume of Migration

According to the survey and inventory conducted by the researchers, it is estimated that the total number of migrants from Tuti Island is 484 persons, in addition to 315 return migrants. The number of migrants from the island constitutes 7.5 percent, 5.7 percent, and 4.5 percent of the total population of the island in 1988, 1991, and 1994 respectively (Table 3.1).

In 1988 the total population of the island was estimated to 8429 persons and the number of migrants was 632 (7.5 percent). The labour force in the island in 1988

was estimated to be 2972, (35 percent of the total population). So the number of migrants constituted about 21 percent of the labour force in the island. In 1994 the labour force in Tuti Island is estimated to be 3476 persons, (32 percent), so the number of migrants constitutes about 14 percent of the labour force in the island.

Table 3.1: Migrants from Tuti Island Against the Total Population of 1988, 1991, and 1994.

Year	Total population	No. of Migrants	% of migrants
1988	8429	632	7.5
1991	9416	537	5.7
1994	10862	484	4.5

Source: 1988 population survey (KUSGA), 1991 national capital population survey, and field survey, 1994.

3.3 Trends of Migration in Tuti Island:

Most of the studies that dealt with the Sudanese migration, indicated that Sudanese migration is a recent phenomenon. All these studies have agreed that migration is of an increasing nature. It is also argued that mass migration started in 1973, when oil prices increased substantially, and the major migration stream was moving towards the Gulf states. Before that date Sudanese migration has got no statistical importance, as it took place in a small and fragmented numbers.

Table 3.2 shows that the proportion of migrants before 1973 is 2 percent, while return migrants who had migrated before 1973 represent 3 percent.

Table 3.2: The Year of Migration Among the Migrants and Return Migrants from Tuti Island (1994)

Years	Migrants		Return migrants	
	No.	%	No.	%
Prior 1973	10	2	10	3
1973 - 1975	20	4	25	8
1976 - 1978	49	10	18	6
1979 - 1981	57	12	45	14
1982 - 1984	52	11	91	29
1985 - 1987	97	20	69	22
1988 - 1990	126	26	41	13
1991 - 1993	73	15	16	5
Total	484	100	315	100

Source: Field survey, 1994.

Figure 3.1: Years of Migration Among Migrants from Tuti Island, 1994.

It is noticeable that from 1973 onwards the migration stream started to increase gradually. For instance, the migrants during the period 1973 - 1975 are 4 percent, while of the return migrants it is 8 percent. From Table 3.2 it is obvious that the highest rate of migration has taken place during the period 1985 - 1987. During this period about 20 percent of the sample has migrated. Among the return migrants the highest rate of migration had taken place during the period 1982 - 1984 (about 29 percent). However, one salient feature is that, from 1973 up to the year 1990 the trend of the migration is an increasing one. The percentage of migrants in 1973 was about 2 percent while in 1990 it reached 26 percent. But during the last period 1991 - 1993, this trend has reversed as the percentage has decreased from 26 percent to 15 percent, which is a considerable decrease. This decrease is justifiable if we know that the major destinations for Tuti migrants is Saudi Arabia and the Gulf states. Thus, since the Second Gulf War, the political disagreement between Sudan and these states has been reflected clearly upon the volume and size of Sudanese migrants, as some new rigid restrictions have been imposed upon certain nationalities. These restrictions have put serious negative effects on the size of Sudanese migrants and definitely among them are those migrants from Tuti Island.

3.4 Countries of Destination

Concerning the destination countries for the migrants from Tuti Island, Table 3.3 shows that the migrants from Tuti Island have a general trend to migrate towards Saudi Arabia and the Gulf states. In addition, Table 3.3 shows that Saudi Arabia had also been a destination for 47 percent of the return migrants. The major receiving country is Saudi Arabia with 53 percent of the total migrants from Tuti Island.

Table 3.3: Distribution of Migrants from Tuti Island by Destination States (1994).

Country	Migrants		Return migrants	
	No	%	No	%
Saudi Arabia	255	53	147	47
U. A. E.	88	18	54	17
Libya	69	14	35	11
Oman	17	4	-	-
Bahrain	16	3	-	-
Yemen	-	-	33	19
Iraq	-	-	35	11
Others	39	8	11	3
Total	484	100	315	100

Source: Field survey, 1994.

The United Arab Emirates (U. A. E.) occupies the second rank among receiving countries with some 18 percent of the total number of migrants from Tuti and 17 percent of the return migrants.

Libya on the other hand, occupies the third place among the Arab countries that receives migrants from Tuti Island. Libya accommodates about 14 percent of the total number of the migrants and 11 percent of the return migrants.

Figure 3.2: Distribution of Migrants from Tuti Island by Destination States (1994).

Source: Based on Table 3.3.

Table 3.3 shows that, Iraq has been one of the major destinations for the migrants from Tuti, and also from the Sudan. But due to the continuous war and conflicts, this country has been looked upon as undesirable destination. Also the unsatisfactory economic return contributed to decrease of the migrant from Tuti to the minimum level. As in the past Iraq accommodated 11 percent of return migrants from Tuti.

3.5 Migrants' Age Structure

Concerning age structure, Table 3.4 shows the age structure for Tuti total population, and migrants from Tuti Island.

Table 3.4: Age Groups Among Migrants from Tuti Compared With Tuti Total Population (1994).

Age group	Tuti total population		Tuti migrants	
	No.	%	No.	%
Under 15 years	2529	30	0	0
15 - 24	2107	25	10	2
25 - 34	1602	19	150	31
35 - 44	1011	12	165	34
45 - 54	590	7	106	22
55 +	590	7	53	11
Total	8429	100	484	100

Source: Compiled from field survey (1994); and 1988 census.

Table 3.4 indicates that migration is a very selective phenomenon as far as the age structure of migrants is concerned. Although people with less than 15 years of age represent 30 percent of the island's population, among the migrants from Tuti no single migrant is included in this age group. Actually this age is below the productive age, so the possibility of persons below this age to contribute to the economic development is neglected. So the offers for those to migrate is quite limited and rare. The age group 15 - 24 represents about 25 percent of the Tuti total population, and only 2 percent of the migrants from Tuti Island. Concerning the age group 15 - 24, although it represents the starting point for the age by which one can be classified as a labour force member, among Tuti migrants it represents a marginal number (2 percent). This may be due to the fact that, during this age most people are involved in education institutions. Actually Tuti Island has got a very bright history with education so a large proportion of Tuti population, in the age of education, are enrolled for education. Migration in most

cases takes place when the potential migrant leaves his education institution whether it is an intermediate, secondary school or a university. So this may explain why migrants in this age group constitute a very marginal percentage.

Figure 3.3: Age Groups of Migrants from Tuti Island and Tuti Population (1994).

Source: Based on Table 3.4.

The number of migrants from Tuti who are classified to be in the age groups 25 - 34 and 35 - 44 are to some extent acceptable, as they have got 31 and 34 percents respectively, compared with 19 percent and 12 percent of the island's population. However, this enhances the argument that migration is a selective phenomenon.

With regard to the other extreme of age structure i.e. the "old age" category, it is noticeable that the number of migrants from Tuti Island in this category, outnumbers those of Tuti total population. For the age groups 45 - 54 and 55 and above, Tuti migrants hold some 22 and 11 percents for those two groups, respectively, while Tuti population holds only 7 percent for each group.

Having in mind this distribution by age group, we can calculate the total percentages of the migrants whose ages are between 15 - 44 years of age. For Tuti community in general this broad age group represents almost 63 percent of the total population of the island. Among the migrants from Tuti those whose ages are in this group represent 67 percent of the total migrants' population.

3.6 The Marital Status Among Migrants

Table 3.5 illustrates the marital status of migrants from Tuti Island. The table shows that 61 percent of the migrants are married. In 1963 EL Hassan estimated the married persons in Tuti to be 65.5 percent. In 1988 it has been reported that in Tuti Island the married persons constitute only 40 percent.

Table 3.5: Marital Status Among the Migrants from Tuti (1994).

Status	S. Arabia		U. A. E.		Oman		Libya		Bahrain		Average
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	Percent
Married	150	59	68	77	13	77	20	29	10	62	61
Unmarried	105	41	20	23	4	23	49	71	6	36	39
Total	255	100	88	100	17	100	69	100	16	100	100

Source: Field survey (1994).

Figure 3.4: Marital Status Among Migrants from Tuti Island (1994).

Source: Based on Table 3.5.

The high percentage of married migrants can be attributed to the good economic conditions in which most of the migrants live, and which enable them to get married and maintain families. Despite the high average rate of marriage among migrants, it is still noticeable that there are some variations among the different destinations. For instance, while the highest rate of marriage among migrants is found in United Arab Emirates, (77 percent), the other extreme has been

occupied by the migrants working in Libya, (29 percent). It seems that the major factor behind this variation in the marriage rate is that each country provides different social and economic environments for the immigrants. These environments include, the financial return and the availability and stability of job opportunities. Table 3.6 shows that the rate of marriage among return migrants (66 percent) is higher than the migrants (61 percent).

Table 3.6: The Marital Status Among the Return Migrants in Tuti Island (1994).

Status	S. Arabia		U. A. E.		Yemen		Libya		Iraq		Others		Average Percent
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	
Married	101	69	37	68	28	85	21	60	8	23	10	91	66
Unmarried	46	31	17	32	5	15	14	40	27	77	1	9	34
Total	147	100	54	100	33	100	35	100	35	100	11	100	100

Source: Field survey (1994).

However, this high percentage of the married persons among the return migrants may be attributed to several reasons. One reason is, it is possible that those return migrants may have migrated during a relatively more satisfactory conditions as far as the financial earnings of migration are concerned, so the possibility of getting married is higher than those migrants who migrated in the last four or five years under different economic conditions. Another reason is that, a considerable proportion of the return migrants is government officials, who had been released through an official contracts which ensure much more satisfactory conditions for the migrants.

Figure 3.5: Marital Status Among the Return Migrants from Tuti Island (1994).

Source: Based on Table 3.6.

Moreover, in the recent times, most of the receiving countries imposed some new regulations to prevent migrants from accompanying their families, this may make the migrant hesitate to get married if he will be unable to accompany his family with him. Also at earlier times, migrants were more accepted as bridegrooms, regardless of their education and occupation. Also this low rate of marriage may indicate that a new disbursement priorities have been developed among migrants. Furthermore, the involvement of girls in education, in recent times, may contribute to this low rate of marriage among migrants, as most of girls now are keen to continue their education at first before getting married.

Although the percentage of the married persons among the migrants is considered as a high percentage, Table 3.7 reveals that the number of migrants

who accompany their families with them is relatively small, as they constitute only about 35 percent of the total married migrants.

Table 3.7: Migrants from Tuti Island who Accompany their Families at their Destinations (1993) (percent).

Status	S. Arabia		U. A. E.		Oman		Libya		Bahrain		Average Percent
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
Accompany families	47	31	31	45	6	46	3	15	4	40	35
Alone	103	69	37	55	7	54	17	85	6	60	65
Total	150	100	68	100	13	100	20	100	10	100	100

Source: Field survey (1994).

Figure 3.6: Migrants from Tuti Island who Accompany their Families at their Destination (1994).

Source: Based on Table 3.7.

Actually this small percentage of the married migrants who accompany their families may be due to the fact that, for the migrant, the major aim and objective from migration is to earn some financial return in the shortest possible period of time. This objective is not easy to be achieved if the migrant accompanies his family with him to the destination, as the money needed for the living expenses will increase substantially to cover the family's needs. But whenever the family lives in Sudan it will be more easy to increase the volume of savings.

3.7 Education Among the Migrants From Tuti Island

With regard to the educational level among migrants from Tuti Island, Table 3.8 shows the migrants from Tuti with their distribution by the education level also this table shows some relevant data concerning the education level of Tuti population.

Table 3.8: Distribution of Migrants by Education Level in Tuti Island (1994).

Level	Tuti migrants		Tuti population	
	No.	%	No.	%
Uneducated	0	0	677	11
Primary	120	25	1825	32
Intermediate	186	39	1141	20
Secondary	118	24	1540	27
Above secondary	60	12	570	10
Total	484	100	5703	100

Source: Field survey 1994, 1988 census.

Figure 3.7: Distribution of Migrants by Education Level Attained in Tuti Island (1994).

Source: Based on Table 3.8.

From the above table it is clear that the uneducated percentage among the migrants from Tuti is almost zero, while it represents some 11 percent among the population of Tuti Island. Among the Tuti Island population the wide spread education level is the primary one since, it represents 32 percent of the total population of the island. But among the migrants from Tuti Island the most wide spread education level is the intermediate level which constitutes some 39 percent of the migrants from Tuti. The higher secondary level among the migrants from Tuti and among population of Tuti are 24 percent for the first and 27 percent for the latter. Also above the secondary level the migrants from Tuti and among the island total population have got nearly similar record as Tuti migrants hold 12 percent while the Tuti population hold 10 percent. This indicates that the level of education among the migrants from Tuti is higher than that of the total population of the island. However, one of the salient features of

the distribution of the migrants from Tuti is that, in most cases outnumbers the percentages of the total population distribution by education level. This at end supports the argument that migration is selective process, as for instance, the higher the educational level among the society, the bigger the number of the potential migrants. So the process of selectivity for migration has taken place and it is found that, migrants are educated persons, compared to the local community population.

3.8 Economic Activities Among the Migrants from Tuti Island

By the economic activities among the migrants we refer to the types of professions and occupations in which the migrants are involved. According to Table 3.9, it is obvious that the most wide spread occupation before migration is the officials or the public and private sector employees.

Table 3.9: The Distribution of Tuti Migrants by Occupation Before and During Migration (1994)

Occupation	Before migration		During migration	
	No	%	No	%
Professionals	44	9	28	6
Officials	165	34	145	30
Technicians	48	10	44	9
Skilled labourer	77	16	44	9
Unskilled labourer	97	20	218	45
Others	53	11	5	1
Total	484	100	484	100

. Source: Field survey (1994).

Figure 3.8: Distribution of Tuti Migrants by Occupation Before and During Migration (1994).

Before Migration

During Migration

Source: Based on Table 3.9.

This sector constitutes 34 percent of the migrants before they migrate to their destination. It is followed, but far behind, by the segment of the unskilled labour which constitutes 20 percent of the then potential migrants.

If we compare the column of the occupation before migration with that of the occupation during migration, one can state that a quite noticeable mobility has taken place along the occupation scale. For instance, the segment of the professionals has decreased from 9 percent before migration to 6 percent of the migrants during migration period. Also the employees (officials) before migration constituted some 34 percent but during the migration this occupation holds 30 percent of the migrants. The same situation is repeated with the technicians and the skilled labourers as they form about 10 and 16 percents respectively before migration, while they constituted 9 and 9 percents of the migrants during migration respectively.

However, the only exceptional case is the unskilled labour segment which has witnessed a remarkable increase from 20 percent before migration to 45 percent during migration period. So it is easy to conclude that there is a clear occupational mobility among the migrants, as they tend to modify and change their career. This can be explained and justified as follows: when a migrant leaves his country abroad the major objective, in most cases, is the financial gains. So when he reaches his destination, his major pressing issue is to find any job to work for survival at the first place, then he may find, in future the better position he looks for. So the migrant, in most cases has the will to change his occupation in accordance with the labour force market. Sometimes the migrant may deny his qualifications to avoid rejection, as if he applies with his all qualifications he may be considered as over qualified. So it seems that when a

migrant seeks for a job he looks for it with the minimum restrictions and the least conditions. Having in mind this situation, it is not surprising to find that the percentage of the unskilled labourer during the migration is the largest proportion, which may be understood as that this segment absorbs some migrants of the other occupations particularly those who prefer to do any work than to stay unemployed.

It may be useful and informative if we can examine the occupation distribution of the migrants from Tuti Island in a comparison with that of the total population in Tuti Island. If this comparison can be held it will enable us to show the similarities and differences between the migrants from Tuti and the Tuti community as a whole. But unfortunately, the data we have accessed, as shown in Table 2.5, is classified, in a rather broad and vague occupations which do not enable us to build such an informative comparison. So the research in this matter can not make a clear cut statement due to the insufficient reliable data.

3.9 Income and Savings Among Migrants:

There are several variables that determine or affect migrants' income. The effect of any single variable may not be the same in all places (Abdelgadir, 1989). Income of migrants is expected to vary with level of education because jobs of different payments require different levels of education and skills. High level of education might widen the range of job opportunities for the migrant and allow them to increase income. Another variable is the duration of residence at the destination which makes considerable differences in migrants' income. One major factor that explains the variation of migrants' income with duration of residence is that it may require some time in the country of

destination before the appropriate work is found. Also migrants' income is expected to be affected by the type of employment and occupation, as different occupations offered different payments.

Table 3.10 show that income of migrants from Tuti Island increases with the level of education, as the income of migrants with post graduate education is almost six times higher than the income of migrants with primary education (Table 3.10).

Also Table 3.10 shows the great effect of the length of residence in destinations. It is found that, the income of migrants from Tuti with short duration in residence is lower than those with long residence in destination. For instance the income of migrants with more than 15 years of residence at destination is almost three times higher than those with 1 - 4 years of residence at destination (Table 3.10). To justify the effect of impact of residence length on migrants' income, Abdelgadir (1989) argues that, it may require some time at destination before appropriate work is found and migrants might take low-paying jobs while searching for well-paying jobs. Also because of the nature of the salary grading structure, employees get promoted and their salaries increase with time. This means that migrant's income from a job increases with time. The longer they stay, the higher their income will be.

The third factor that affects the migrants' income is the occupation. As shown in Table 3.10 the type of occupation affect the income of migrants from Tuti Island. For instance, professional migrants receive income as high as six times than that of the unskilled labourers (Table 3.10). The effect of occupation is influenced by the sector in which the migrant is employed. As the higher

income is usually offered by the public sector in all destinations. Also some of the migrants, namely technicians, skilled labourers, and unskilled labourers are self-employed. This may increase the income by doubling or intensifying the load to gain more income.

Table 3.10: Migrants' Average Annual Income and Savings by Level of Education, Duration of Residence in Destination, and Occupation, Tuti Island, 1994.

Variable	Average Income \$	Savings as % of the income
Level of education:		
Primary	3900	28
Intermediate	6384	33
Secondary	12000	35
Graduate	14952	36
Post graduate	22392	40
Duration of Residence at Destination (years)		
1 - 4	11052	30
5 - 9	12036	35
10 - 14	18012	38
15 +	33852	38
Occupation:		
Professionals	22392	40
Officials	12480	33
Technicians	12600	35
Skilled labourers	13920	30
Unskilled labourers	3660	23

Source: Field survey, 1994.

Concerning the volume of savings of migrants from Tuti Island, Table 3.10 also shows that the level of education, duration of residence, and the occupation affect the volume of saving. From Table 3.10 it is evident that the percentage of saving increases with the increase in the level of education. While the saving of a migrant with primary level of education is about 28 percent of the average income, the saving of a migrant with post graduate level of education is about 40 percent of the migrant's income. Also the duration of migrants in destination is positively associated with the migrant's saving, as the longer the duration at the destination, the higher the percentage of savings. Since education and profession are complementary, it is not surprising to find a clear relation between the volume of savings and the occupation. For instance, while the savings of professionals is about 40 percent of their income, the savings of unskilled labourers is about 23 percent of their income.

3.10 Remittances by Migrants

With regard to the remittances sent back to the island by migrants, the field survey revealed that 88 percent of the migrants in the sample remit money to their families in Tuti Island. Among the return migrants, 85 percent of the sample responded that they have used to remit money. Table 3.11 shows the frequency of the flow of remittances to families in Tuti Island. The table shows that the majority of migrants (53 percent of the sample) sent their remittances on regular basis (monthly). Also a large proportion of the return migrants (40 percent of the sample) had used to send their remittances on regular basis (monthly).

Table 3.11: The Frequency of Remittances Flow in Tuti Island, 1994.

Frequency	Migrants		Return migrants	
	No	%	No	%
Regular (monthly)	34	53	16	40
Every two months	14	22	11	28
More than two months	16	25	13	32
Total	64	100	40	100

Source: Field survey, 1994.

It was found that most of the remittances have been sent through friends and relative of the migrants as about 55 percent of the sample reported that they sent money with relative and friend migrants who come to Tuti in vacations. The second channel by which money is remitted, as shown in Table 3.12, is banking system (30 percent).

Table 3.12: Channels of Transferring Remittances by Migrants, Tuti Island, 1994.

Channel	Migrants		Return migrants	
	No	%	No	%
Banking system	19	30	10	25
Merchants	9	14	7	17.5
Friends & relatives	36	56	23	57.5
Total	64	100	40	100

Source: Filed survey, 1994.

Concerning the volume of remittances sent by migrants, Table 3.13 shows that there are some variables that affect the volume of remittances. We have

considered four variables which include, level of education, duration of migration, occupation, and the location of migrants' family, whether lives at destination or in Tuti Island.

Evidences from the field survey indicated that the existence of families with migrants at destinations has a negative relation with the volume of savings and remittances. About 87 percent of the sample believe that if families accompany migrants this will reduce the net financial return of migration.

Table 3.13 shows that the average size of remittances increased with the level of education. Migrants with secondary education remit, on average, twice as high as those with primary education. Migrants with graduate education remit more than twice as much as those with intermediate education. While post-graduate migrants remit, on average, four times as much as those with the primary education. Although the size of remittances increase with the level of education. Table 3.13 indicates that the proportion of migrants' income remitted to the island decreases with the level of education. The proportion of income remitted ranges from 23 percent for migrants with primary level of education to 16 percent for those with post-graduate education. The reason for the decrease in the proportion of income remitted with the level of education could be related to the effects of education on migrants' income. Because, generally, migrants with low level of education have low average annual income, remittances represent a large proportion of their income. Migrants with higher level of education have a high average annual income and, although they remit more, the amounts they remit represent a small proportion of their income. Also data on the duration of migration, in Table 3.13, shows an increase in the average amount of remittances over time. This may be due to

**Table 3.13: Average Annual Remittances by Level of Education,
Duration of Migration, Occupation and Location of Family,
Tuti Island, 1994.**

Variable	Annual income (\$)	Annual Remittances (\$)	Remittances % of income
Level of Education			
Primary	3900	900	23
Intermediate	6384	1080	17
Secondary	12000	1800	15
Graduate	14952	2400	16
Post-graduate	22392	3672	16
Duration of Migration			
1 - 4	11052	1216	11
5 - 9	12024	1563	13
10 - 14	18012	3242	18
15 +	33852	3385	10
Occupation			
Professionals	22392	3672	16
Officials	12480	2400	19
Technicians	12600	1500	12
Skilled labourers	19800	2100	11
Unskilled labourers	3660	1080	29
Family in Tuti Island	13056	3264	25
Family in destination	13056	1436	11

Source: Field survey, 1994.

the fact that migrants take some time to become established. Also migrants during their early years of migration have low average annual income and their income increases over time and then do their remittances. Also from Table 3.13, it is noticed that the size of remittances increase accordingly with the occupational scale. It is not surprising to find that income of migrant with high level of occupation receive higher income, and the size of their remittances is also higher. For instance, the remittances of a professional migrant is almost three times as much as those remittances of the labour migrants. Also the same thing happened with the level of education repeated with the occupation. As the proportion of the remittances from the income decreases with the increase in the occupational level of the migrants, the proportion of remittances from the income ranges from 16 percent for the professional migrant, to 29 percent for the labour migrant.

Another feature shown in Table 3.13, concerning the size of remittance, is that when migrants accompany their families to their destination this affects negatively average size of remittances. The size of remittances sent to the island when the family lives in Tuti Island is 25 percent of the migrants' income, while it is only 11 percent when the family lives at destination with the migrant.

CHAPTER FOUR

THE ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION AND REMITTANCES ON TUTI ISLAND COMMUNITY

CHAPTER FOUR

The Economic Impacts of Migration on Tuti Island Community

4.1 Introduction

As stated earlier, the volume of migration from Tuti Island constitutes a reasonable proportion of the total population of the island. So it is believed that this volume of migration affects the economic aspects of life in Tuti Island in different ways. This chapter aims at examining and evaluating the economic impact of migration and re remittances on Tuti Island community. It reviews the impact of migration and remittances on the migrant family income, and the income distribution in the island. Also this chapter reviews the disbursement of remittances, and the pattern of investment among the migrants from Tuti and their families. Also it examines the level and rate of dependency in Tuti Island community upon the migrants from the island.

There has been a continuous debate on the major factors that urge people to migrate. From the field survey, it is found that among the migrants from Tuti Island, the major reasons behind migration are revolving around the "*Neoclassical Economic Theory*". That is, the economic conditions before migration are the major pushing factors. About 63 percent of the migrants stated that they were not satisfied with their economic status before migration. The second mentioned reason for migration is that they intended to build house, get married, and to secure more prospectus future for their families.

The field survey showed that about 30 percent of the migrants' sample have migrated without employment authorization. Being a migrant with or without work permit, this would, definitely, affect the job and the salary the migrant may get.

Although more than 60 percent of the sample involved in sectors and jobs similar to those they have used to do in the Sudan, still 65 percent of the sample considered themselves as unsatisfied with their jobs and the salaries they are paid. This is build mainly upon the comparison with their plans and aspirations.

However, about 89 percent of the sample reported that they have acquired some new experience and skills from their migration. Table 4.1 shows much more on this issue.

Table 4.1: Migration and Acquiring New Skills and Experience in Tuti Island, 1994.

Type of training	Migrants	
	No. of respondents	%
In-service training	48	66
Special course at destination	9	12
Overseas training	-	-
Personal contact with foreigners	55	75

Source: Field survey, 1994.

4.2 Remittances and Family Income:

The field survey conducted among migrants from Tuti Island showed that 88 percent of the migrants' sample remit money to their families in the island. Although the percentage of the remittances vary according to level of income, education, and occupation, it is still valid that, the remittances sent by migrants to their families affect the income among these families. However, the field survey shows that, remittances constitute a considerable proportion of the migrants' family income in Tuti Island. Table 4.2 shows that 71.5 percent of the surveyed sample reported that remittances constitute about 81 - 100 percent of the family income. About 13 percent indicate that remittances constitute about 61 - 80 percent of the family income. In other words, about 85 percent of the surveyed sample reported that remittances represent 61 - 100 percent of their income (Table 4.2).

Table 4.2: Remittances and Family Income as Reported by Households and Migrants from Tuti Island, (%) 1994.

Remittances as % of the family income	Migrants		Households		Average
	No.	%	No.	%	%
100 - 81	45	70	47	73	71.5
80 - 61	8	12	9	14	13
60 - 41	6	10	5	8	9
40 - 21	4	6	1	2	3
20 - 1	1	2	2	3	2.5
Total	64	100	64	100	100

Source: Field survey, 1994.

On the other hand, about 16 percent of the surveyed sample reported that the remittances constitute about 60 - 1 percent of the family income. The major observation in this concern is that, remittances sent by migrants from Tuti Island to their families constitute a considerable proportion of the family income. Thus, remittances in Tuti Island play significant role in supporting of the families income and economics.

The field survey revealed that the average annual remittances sent by migrants from Tuti Island range between 10 percent of the migrant average annual income (about \$ 1532) up to 29 percent of the migrant average annual income (about \$ 4443). This variation in the size of remittances is influenced mainly, as shown earlier, by the migrants' level of income, education, occupation, and duration of migration (Table 3.13). Also the field survey indicated that, the average annual remittances among migrants from Tuti Island is 16 percent of their average annual income (about \$ 2452).

Having in mind that, large proportion of migrants from Tuti send remittances, coupled with the fact that the island community is, to a large extent, an economically and socially homogeneous society. It is an expected finding that remittances tend to increase and raise income among migrants' families.

Most of the Tuti Islands' population can be classified as "limited income receipts", whether from public or private sector, with a narrow range and variations concerning level of income. The remittances send by migrants to their families add some new financial resources to these households and hence this tends to create inequality in income distribution among the island community. Moreover, remittances may add some financial resources (capital)

which can be used as productive investment to generate more income for the migrant's family. Also, remittances play an important role in diversification of income risks by providing the family with more financial return.

Furthermore, it is noticeable that remittances have introduced much wider differentiation, and they intensified stratification among the island economic structure. It is also noticeable that most of the migrant households that receive remittances are relatively prosperous compared to non-migrants households in Tuti Island.

4.3 Disbursement of Remittances

Among the majority of migrants who remit money to their families, only 20 percent of them reported that they remit money but they do not know how these remittances are spent by families, while the majority (80 percent) know how and where the remittances are spent.

When a question about the major disbursement of remittances is raised, different view points have been reported. Table 4.3, shows the priorities of remittances disbursement as identified by migrants, as well as the migrant households.

One salient point, as far as remittances disbursement is concerned, is that the two categories have pointed out the expenses on the every day needs to be the first priority of disbursement. According to the migrants, this item consumes at most 60 percent of the remitted money, and the migrant households reported

that this type of disbursement consumes, on average, about 65 percent of the remittances (Table 4.3).

For the second priority, a slight difference occurs, as education fees and expenses have been reported by migrants to absorb 13 percent of remittances and households have reported the construction and furnishment of houses priority which consumes 18 percent of the remittances.

House-building is mentioned as the third priority of disbursement by migrants. They reported that this item absorbs about 13 percent of the remittances. For the households the third priority is education expenses and fees which consumes about 6 percent of the remitted money.

While 80 percent of the sample know how and where the remittances are spent, only 58 percent of the sample reported that they are used to intervene in the decisions made by families concerning the priority of remittances disbursement.

Table 4.3: Priorities of Remittances Disbursement, Tuti Island, 1994.

Priority	Migrants		Households	
	Type of disbursement	As % of the remittances	Type of disbursement	As % of the remittances
First	Purchase of consumption goods to meet everyday needs to support families.	60	Purchase of consumption goods to meet everyday needs to support families.	65
Second	Education of sons, daughters and other siblings.	13	Construction and furnishment of houses.	18
Third	Construction and furnishment of houses.	13	Education of sons, daughters and other siblings.	6
Fourth	Investment in terms of land acquisition, houses, private transport and bank shares.	6	Financing marriage ceremonial celebration for different family members.	4
Fifth	Financing marriage ceremonial celebration for different members of family.	3	Investment in terms of land acquisition, houses and private transport.	4
Sixth	Contribution to different social public ceremonies.	3	Expenses of medical care and treatment for family members.	3
Seventh	Expenses of medical care and treatment for family members.	2		

Source: Field survey, 1994.

Concerning the financial support of migrants to different socio-economic activities within the family units, the results shown in Table 4.4 reflect that the

most supported activity by migrants is the furnishment of the family's house, as 64 percent of the sample reported that they have contributed to this activity. This is followed by financing marriage ceremonial celebrations which have been supported by almost 62 percent of the surveyed sample. The support of pilgrimage and Omra of the parents occupy the third rank among the activities supported by migrants, as about 47 percent of the sample have supported this activity. The fourth rank among the activities supported by migrants is occupied by construction of new houses for migrants themselves, as 46 percent have reported that they contributed to building of new houses. Then followed by both medical treatment abroad for some relatives and friends, as well as pay-off debts. For both medical treatment and debt payments' about 39 percent of the sample have reported that they have contributed to these activities.

Table 4.4: Family Socio-economic Activities Supported by Migrants, Tuti Island, 1994.

Type of activity	Migrants		Households		Average
	No	%	No	%	%
Financing marriage ceremonies.	49	67	52	71	62
Furnishment of family's house	50	69	52	71	64
Construction of new houses	30	41	26	36	46
Medical treatment abroad	36	49	17	23	39
Pay-off debts	34	47	30	41	39
Parents' pilgrimage and Omra	46	63	30	41	47
Relatives' pilgrimage and Omra	42	57	15	20.5	33.5
Purchase of real-estate for relatives	4	6	17	23	12
Education abroad	15	20	13	18	17
Expenses of sibling's travel	21	29	11	15	22

Source: Field survey, 1994.

As seen in Table 4.3, migrants and migrant households have reported a little bit different priorities for remittances disbursement. Interestingly when the two categories were requested to identify the major four achievements accomplished through remittances, the categories have almost reported typical achievements. Table 4.5 shows that the first achievement mentioned by migrants and households is the construction and/or maintenance of the house. Also the second achievement is typical among the two categories, i.e. the improvement of the living standards of the families. The third and the fourth achievements accomplished by the remitted money, however, are revolving around education for siblings, financing marriage ceremonial celebrations and investment. The trend among the migrants and household to indicate the same achievements may reflect that, there is some sort of thought similarities among the two categories concerning the usage of remittances.

Table 4.5: Major Achievements Accomplished Through Remittances, Tuti Island, 1994.

Achievement	Migrants	Households
First	Construction and maintenance of houses.	Construction and maintenance of houses.
Second	Improvement of the living standards of the family.	Improvement of the living standards of the family.
Third	Marriage and maintain families as well as education of siblings.	Education for siblings in and outside Sudan and finance marriage celebration among family.
Fourth	Establishment of some investments to generate income.	Pilgrimage and Omra as well as medical treatment.

Source: Field survey, 1994.

The field survey revealed that about 54 percent of the migrants' sample stated that they have built private houses. Among the return migrants, about 68 percent of the sample had built their own houses. It could be noticed that, from Table 4.5 and these percentages, that the house-building is one of the most common objective for migration and desirable area of remittances disbursement.

Furthermore, the amount of money pumped into house-building is estimated, on average, by migrants to be around \$ 20353, which is a large sum of money. Having in mind that the average savings of migrants from Tuti Island is about 34 percent of their annual income, the average annual income is estimated to be \$ 15322, then the annual saving is estimated to be \$ 5209. In other words, the cost of house-building is almost equivalent to the average annual savings for a period of four years.

Also it is found that, of those who have not built houses yet, about 61 percent have already acquired lands, of whom about 59 percent have started the house-building process. Moreover, the surveyed sample revealed that the average number of land plots possessed by migrants inside Tuti Island is about 1.3 plots. While outside the island the average number of plots is about 0.8 plots. Concerning return migrants, the average number of land plots is about 1.5. However, outside the island, return migrants possessed about 0.3 plots per migrant.

Actually the difference between migrants and return migrants may due to availability of land offered for sale. In recent times, due to the high rate of land selling, it is not easy to get a plot of land inside the island. So among migrants

there is a trend to purchase lands outside the island if it is not easy to get it inside the island. For return migrants it was possible for them to acquire land plots as competition on land acquisition was less than today.

Some of the field work results showed that about 24 percent of the migrants have owned houses outside the island, and about 28 percent of the return migrants have owned houses outside the island.

When trying to describe the architectural and structural style of those houses, Table 4.6 shows that most of the migrants' houses are one-floor houses (43 percent). But considerable proportion (34 percent) have built two-floor houses.

It is evident that some obvious improvements on the houses style, pattern, and services have taken place.

Table 4.6: Migration and Style of Houses, Tuti Island, 1994

Style of house	Migrants	
	No	%
Villa	2	3
Two-floor	25	34
Potentially two-floor	15	20
Ordinary	31	43

Source: Field survey, 1994.

In the past nearly all the houses in the island were built by local materials and bricks. But in the recent days, where the volume of migration has increased substantially, the impact of migration on the house-building materials is quite

obvious. The prevailing materials now used in house-building is cement and bricks. Also the overwhelming pattern of houses are the one-complex building which is a new style of building, which has been recently adopted by migrants. Moreover, the living atmosphere inside the houses of migrants seems to be more comfortable and attractive. Some 36 percent of the migrants' houses are with gardens. Among the return migrants about 40 percent of the houses include gardens. Also about 74 percent of the surveyed sample has reported that their houses are well-drained as they use siphons. Certainly the use of siphons for water drainage will put some positive impact on the environmental health conditions inside the island, or at least at the areas surrounded these houses.

Through investigation about the durable consumer goods, it is found, as shown in Table 4.7, that the ownership of the durable consumer goods consumes a major proportion of the remitted money. Table 4.7 shows that migrants have owned different types of durable goods. For instance, more than 90 percent of the migrants' surveyed sample own televisions, electrical irons, and refrigerators, which is a very high proportion. In 1987 it was found that about 93 percent of the Sudanese migrants own television, and 94 percent owned refrigerators (Hamed and Ahmed, 1988). Also among migrants from Tuti Island, about 70 percent have owned tape recorders, washing machines, and carpet. Although some equipment like cookers, and deep freezers can be considered as a relatively modern and not commonly used in Tuti Island community, but high proportion of the sample reported that they have owned these items.

Table 4.7: The Ownership of Durable Consumer Goods Among Migrants, Tuti Island, 1994.

Item	Migrants		Household		Average
	No	%	No	%	%
Television	66	91	65	89	90
Video	38	52	36	50	51
Refrigerator	71	98	66	91	94.5
Deep freezer	33	45	33	45	45
Tape recorder	64	88	63	86	87
Air cooler	33	45	34	47	46
Personal car	11	15	13	18	16.5
Washing machine	55	76	58	80	78
Electric iron	71	98	71	97	97.5
Cooker	29	40	32	44	42
Carpet	55	75	56	77	76

Source: Field survey, 1994.

Concerning the non-monetary remittances, it is found that some 62 percent of the migrants reported that they are used to remit irregularly. Among the return migrants, about 55 percent of the sample reported that they had used to send non-monetary remittances. The most prominent items which are sent by migrants are the expensive tinned food, fashionable foreign clothing, modern building materials, contemporary home furnishings, fancy electrical appliances, medicines and many other symbols of modernization.

To maintain good ties with relatives and friends, it is found that about 76 percent of the migrants' sample are keen to provide relatives and friends with

gifts and presents. It is estimated that the migrants are used to spend, on average, about 10 percent of their annual incomes in terms of gifts and presents. This percentage reflects that a considerable proportion of migrants are keen to develop strong ties with their relatives and friends in the island.

4.4 Patterns of Investment

The field survey revealed that about 39 percent of the respondents in our sample have already initiated and established some sort of investment. The major patterns of investment initiated by migrants are the real-estate, i.e. land-acquisition and house-building. It is found that a considerable proportion of migrants have acquired land plots whether in or outside Tuti Island. Also they tend to build houses and rent-out these houses to secure additional income for the family. Another pattern of investment is in terms of small-scale commercial business, i.e. establishment of shops and super-markets. The field survey revealed that almost 35 percent of the small-scale commercial business in Tuti Island is initiated, established and run by migrants and their families, although nearly all of these shops are retailing trade shops. But, among them, the most outstanding ones are those working in the provision of gas for house use. Actually two of the migrants have established agencies for Total and Abarci Gas distribution. Those two agencies are offering appreciated services in the island.

Although, for non-migrants, land plots are kept for the future use for the members of the family, it is found among migrants that land-acquisition is seen as a sort of investment for the savings. In the past, lands in Tuti Island are traditionally divided into two major uses, i.e. residential and agricultural uses.

But by the high rate of land acquisition in the island, the residential lands have expanded on the expenses of the agricultural ones. Among migrants, it is found that some of them have own more than three plots. Having in mind that Tuti is an island, with a quite limited lands, the trend among migrants to acquire lands has pushed the land prices to increase substantially. Although the lands of Tuti Island are classified as non-residential lands by the Survey Department, where it lacks the proper public services, still the prices of land plots in the island is not less, if not more, than the prices outside the island. Actually the lack of services is fully compensated by the well-built social context in which those lands are located.

Actually migrants from Tuti Island tend to purchase land plots to invest their money, as they are confident that the prices of lands will not decrease. Some of them used to sell some of their land to cover the house-building expenses.

Moreover, some of the migrants from Tuti Island have pumped their savings into the field of inland transport. In the past the inland means of transport inside the island was run by a share-holding company. Nowadays, private cars and minibuses have become available. The number of cars that are working in this sector is 21 cars. Out of this number 9 cars are owned by migrants. That is, about 43 percent of the transport sector in Tuti Island is run by migrants.

While trying to assess the impact of migration on the economic conditions of migrants and households compared to these conditions before migration, Table 4.8 shows that about 40 percent of migrants sample considered their present economic conditions as far better compared to the period before migration. While about 48 percent of the sample considered their economic conditions

just better than before migration, and the rest of the sample (12 percent) reported that their conditions are as the same as before migration. On the other hand, 40 percent of the households have considered their economic conditions as far better compared to the period before migration.

Table 4.8: Economic Conditions Before and After Migration, Tuti Island, 1994.

Economic condition	Migrants		Households		Average %
	No	%	No	%	
Far better	29	40	29	40	40
Better	35	48	37	51	49.5
The same	9	12	6	8	10
Worse	-	-	1	1	0.5
Total	73	100	73	100	100

Source: Field survey, 1994.

About 51 percent considered their conditions as better, while only 8 percent of the sample reported that they consider their conditions as the same as before migration, and a very marginal segment (only 1 percent) considered their economic conditions as worse as before migration. In other words, it is obvious that the overwhelming majority from migrants (91 percent) perceived their economic conditions as better than those before migration. Also about 88 percent of the households believe that they are in better economic conditions compared to their conditions before migration.

4.5 Dependency on Migrants

The field survey showed that there is a high ratio of dependency on migrants from Tuti Island. It is found that the average number of persons entirely dependent on migrant is 4.2 persons. While the average number of persons who are partially dependent on migrants is 5.1 persons.

Moreover, it is reported that about 62 percent of migrants' sample have reported that their families are entirely dependent on them. About 27 percent of the sample have reported that their families are partially dependent upon them, while the rest of the sample (11 percent) have reported that their families are independent upon them.

These figures, however, reflect that there is a high rate of dependency on migrants in Tuti Island community.

4.6 Return Migrants

In addition to the 484 migrants from Tuti Island, the field survey showed that there are 315 return migrants from Tuti Island. The field survey showed that the major destinations for the return migrants from Tuti Island, were Saudi Arabia which accommodated 47 percent of the return migrants, followed by United Arab Emirates which accommodated 17 percent of the return migrant. Then Libya, Iraq, and Yemen. The three destinations accommodated the same percentage (11 percent of the return migrants of Tuti Island). However, the field survey found that the large proportion of the return migrants from Tuti come home after 1990 (about 47 percent).

Concerning the reasons that urge the return migrants to migrate. About 70 percent of the sample reported that their unsatisfactory economic conditions had pushed them abroad. The field survey revealed that out of the total return migrants about 47 percent had migrated without work permit and authorization. Most of them entered their destinations as visitors or for Omra and Pilgrimage, and then they had stayed there and engaged into some sort of work. Some had issued proper documents for their employment later, and some had not.

Concerning the reasons behind the termination of their migration, the field survey showed that about 63 percent of the sample had come home mainly because their contracts had been terminated. About 20 percent of the sample reported that they had returned home voluntarily, and the rest of the sample, 17 percent, had come home because they had no proper work permit and authorization.

Concerning the uses made of savings and remittances by the return migrants, it is found that 75 percent of the sample believe that their remittances and savings had been spent on consumption rather than productive activities. The remaining 25 percent believe that some of their remittances and savings had been used for investment. The major areas of investment among the return migrants were transportation, small-scale, commercial business (shops), land-acquisition, and building of houses to be rent-out to secure additional income for families.

But the most outstanding investment executed by return migrants in the field of transport is the river transport scheme which was initiated just two years ago.

Since 1960's, the only regular outlet from Tuti Island was the ferry known as "Bantoun". This ferry was owned by the River Transport Corporation (RTC). Due to the old fashioned ferries used by RTC and the chronic shortage of spare parts as well as many other administrative problems, the river transport to and from Tuti Island was considered as a real headache for the people of Tuti. It was one of the most time-consuming factors for the people of Tuti. In 1992 one of the return migrants from Tuti decided to invest in this sector, i.e. the river transport, and he has got a license to operate three motor boats between Khartoum and Tuti Island. Actually this scheme is one of the most successful and fruitful investments in the island. It has provided the island with a more regular and stable river transport means. On the other hand this project has also provided the owner with a very satisfactory financial return.

With regard to the major achievements accomplished by remittances and savings, return migrants indicated that the construction of houses (49 percent of the sample), the improvement of the family's standards of living (30 percent of the sample), finance of the marriage ceremonial celebrations in the family (12 percent of the sample), and purchase of real-estate (lands, houses) (9 percent of the sample).

Moreover, it is also found that about 28 percent of the sample owned houses outside Tuti Island. But if we consider all return migrants who had owned houses, whether in or outside the island, the percentage raises to be 68 percent of the return migrants sample. Also return migrants from Tuti Island tend to own some of the durable consumer goods. The field survey showed that high percentages of the return migrants had own items of the electric equipment

such as televisions, video, refrigerator, air cooler, washing machines, deep freezers, ... etc.

Concerning type of occupation practiced by the return migrants, the field survey showed a wide variation in the occupations practiced before, during and after migration. Although the majority of the return migrants were officials (public sector), after return home, this majority tend to work in the private sector or to work as self-employed. This mainly because of the low rates of wages among the public sector.

Moreover, although large proportion of the return migrants sample (65 percent) had acquired some new skills and experiences in their destinations, they refused to continue in the same work when they come back to the Sudan. They preferred to modify their occupation to find a job with more financial return.

The most interesting point is that, the field survey showed that about 75 percent of the sample opt to migrate again for any destination if there is a chance for them.

To sum up, it seems to be that the return migrants from Tuti Island had contributed to improve the living standards of their families, but contributed very marginally in the services sector, to the improvement of the community welfare as a whole, and still they are thinking that they may migrate again to improve their economic conditions and to get some satisfactory standard of living for their families.

4.7 Summary

This chapter examined the economic impact of migration and remittances in Tuti Island community. It is found that the impact of remittances on family income is considerable as about 85 percent of the sample reported that remittances represent 61 - 100 percent of their family income. It is also argued that remittances tend to increase and raise income among migrants' families, and they add some new financial resources to these families, hence this tends to create inequality in income distribution among the island community, and they also introduce some economic stratification among the island economic structure. Concerning the disbursement of remittances it is found that most of the remittances (62.5 percent) is used for consumption goods for family. The rest of the remittances is used for education and house construction and maintenance. Only 5 percent of the remittances is directed towards investment. Migrants from Tuti Island support a wide variety of family socio-economic activities with considerable volume of remittances, such as marriage, education, pilgrimage, house constructions, ... etc. However, the construction of the family's house and improvement of living standard of the migrant's family have been raised as the major achievements accomplished by remittances. Competition on land-acquisition has resulted in an increasing in the land prices in Tuti Island.

Also a new style of building (one-complex) with more attractive atmosphere has been adopted by migrants in Tuti Island. Moreover, it is found that a large proportion from the sample owned different items from the durable consumer goods. With regard to investment, it is found that small proportion of the sample has initiated some sort of investment. The wide spread investment is

the land-acquisition, house-building for rent-out, in addition to small-scale commercial business and transportation. It is also found that there is a high rate of dependency on migrants among the community of Tuti Island. Concerning the return migrants from Tuti Island it is argued that they contributed a lot to their families and marginally, with some exceptions, to the island community, and it is also found that most of them opt to migrate again if they get the chance.

CHAPTER FIVE

THE SOCIAL IMPACT OF MIGRATION ON TUTI ISLAND COMMUNITY

CHAPTER FIVE

THE SOCIAL IMPACTS OF MIGRATION ON TUTI ISLAND COMMUNITY

5.1 Introduction:

It has always been argued that migration is one of the influential human phenomenon that brings a wide variety of social change for both the sending and receiving societies. This chapter is intended to study the social impacts of migration in Tuti Island as a sending society. It examines the impact of migration on the marriage institution in Tuti Island. Also this chapter reviews the social stratification brought to the island by migration. It also reviews the impact of migration on the education and health service centers in the island. Moreover, this chapter shows the relationships between migrants from the island and their community, and finally it reveals the support of migrants from the island to some of the public activities in the island.

5.2 Migration and Marriage Institution

Throughout history Tuti Island community has got a well-recognized reputation concerning its extremely homogeneous social structure compared to any other communities of the surrounding areas.

It is evident that the community of Tuti Island has the ability to maintain its own internal social and cultural institutions to tackle the different aspects of life.

However, one of the most prominent social institutions adopted in Tuti Island is referred to as *Kora* Marriage System. This marriage system is basically an attempt to ease the procedures of marriage celebrations. It emphasizes the reduction of the cost of marriage by determining the maximum number of items brought by the bridegroom to his bride and to minimize the expenditure spend by husband on the wedding-feast. In most cases, it is arranged that large number of wedding celebrations take place collectively in one day. The major objective behind *Kora* system is to remove the financial constraints that prohibit young couples from getting married.

It is said that this system was emerged in Tuti Island not less than a century ago. As time passes, the essence of this system has been diffused to several other communities.

In the past, *Kora* marriage system was extremely predominant in Tuti Island. Abdelgadir (1989) argued that, migration affects some rural institutions such as marriage. Traditionally marriages to relatives have been preferred, and to a very considerable extent, parents of both males and females arrange for such a marriage to take place. Having in mind this argument, it is planned that this research will try to assess the impact of migration on the traditional marriage institutions in Tuti Island.

Concerning the preferential marriage pattern, Lobban (1982) stated that the first cousins in the Sudan are considered to be ideal spouses. The most desired spouse with reference to a male ego would be the father's brother's daughter, or parallel cousin. However, in Tuti Island community there is a general tendency for lineage endogamy. In other words, most spouses in Tuti are kin and are

from the same family the bridegroom. These relations were statistically significant in 1970-72 (84 percent) and continued to be so in 1979-80 (Lobban, 1982; 67).

Recently, our field survey revealed the same finding, i.e. marriage to relative is the most predominant in the island. It is found that about 87 percent of the married migrants are married to spouse from Tuti, while only 13 percent of them married to spouse from outside. This small portion of spouse from outside the island reflects that, there is a strong social ties prevailing in Tuti community. These ties make it quite difficult for migrants to marry from outside the island.

Moreover, it was found that about 69 percent of the married migrants have got married to their first-cousins, while 31 percent of the married sample reported that they have no clear kin relations to their spouses. Having in mind the strong family ties in Tuti Island community, it seems that the 31 percent is a considerable portion which may introduce a new trend among the island community as far as mate selection is concerned.

With regard to the opinion of migrants about *Kora* Marriage System, it was found that about 60 percent of the sample support this marriage system, 25 percent support the system with some reservations, and 15 percent reported that they are anti-*Kora* system.

However, when the married migrants were asked whether they had got married by *Kora* marriage system, about 42 percent of the sample reported that they had got married by this system. The majority (58 percent) of the married

sample reported that they had not got married by *Kora* system. On the other hand, among the return migrants about 66 percent of the married segment have reported that they had got married by this system, and (36 percent) had not got married by this system.

But the most astonishing finding is that, among the unmarried migrants about 63 percent do not plan to get married through *Kora* marriage system, i.e. the majority of the migrants plan not to marry according to *Kora* system regulations. This indicates that during the recent future it is expected that the traditional marriage institution, i.e. *Kora* marriage system, will be affected by the thoughts prevailing among migrants.

It has been stated earlier that about 67 percent of the sample supported and financed marriage ceremonial celebrations for member of their families. The sample survey showed that among those who supported marriage celebrations, 48 percent paid the entire expenses of the celebrations, and about 60 percent of them purchased the complete clothing sets for the bride "sheala" on behalf of the groom. Also among those who have supported marriage celebrations, about 79 percent have purchased some sets of "sheala" and 75 percent of the sample have offered partial financial support for the celebration. (Table 5.1)

Thus, there is a considerable support and contribution from migrants to marriage in Tuti Island. Among the interviewed migrants it is found that some of them have purchased complete sets of sheala for more than five different husbands. Certainly this huge support would put a real positive impact on marriage, by accelerating the marriage rate in Tuti Island.

Table 5.1: Migrants' Support to Marriage Ceremonies in Tuti Island, 1994.

Type of support	Migrants		Return migrants	
	No. of migrants	%	No. of return migrants	%
Entire expenses	155	48	57	30
Complete sheala	194	60	127	67
Parts of sheala	256	79	132	70
Some financial support	243	75	153	81

Source: Field survey, 1994.

Concerning the impact of migration on the rate of marriage in Tuti Island community, Table 5.2 shows that during the period 1992 - 1994, the number of marriage ceremonies among migrants' families is higher than the number of marriage ceremonies among the non-migrants families. As shown in Table 5.2, in 1992, the number of marriage ceremonies among the migrants' families was 27 out of 39 which constitutes 69 percent of the total marriage ceremonies took place at that year-in Tuti. In 1993 the percentage of the marriage ceremonies among migrants' families was 65, and in 1994 it was about 67 percent. So on average, marriage ceremonies among migrants' families constitute about 67 percent of the total ceremonies arranged in the mentioned period.

This high rate of marriage among the migrants' families may be due to the fact that, migrants are used to remove all the constraints facing the marriage procedures, mainly the financial cost of the celebration. The field survey showed that large proportion of migrants (67 percent of the sample) contributed to finance the marriage celebrations for their family members, as well as their friends.

Table 5.2: Number of Marriage Ceremonies in Tuti Island, 1992 - 1994.

Marriage in	1992		1993		1994		Average %
	No. of ceremonies	%	No. of ceremonies	%	No. of ceremonies	%	
Non-migrants' families	12	31	16	35	14	33	33
Migrants' families	27	69	30	65	29	67	67
Total	39	100	46	100		100	100

Source: Field survey, 1994.

5.3 Migration and Education

With regard to migrants' contribution to education in their families it was found that some 70 percent of the migrants are supporting some members of their families who are pursuing their education whether in Sudan or abroad.

This high percentage is linked to the increasing number of students from Tuti Island who have enrolled into private higher education institutions in Sudan and the large number of students who seek education abroad, especially in Egypt and India.

Concerning the education of migrants themselves, it was found that about 44 percent of the migrants have some ideas about continuing their education, but out of those 44 percent only 31 percent (about 10 migrants) have actually started or completed a study course to improve their qualifications. About four migrants have involved into some distance education programmes seeking

academic degrees, while the rest of migrants have started some occupational and professional training, i.e. non-degree studies.

5.4 Migration and Social Stratification:

The field survey among migrants from Tuti Island showed that, there is a considerable variation between migrants' and non-migrants' families, as far as level of income is concerned. This is mainly because migrants' household have an access to some additional financial resources, which come from remittances.

Evidence from the field survey indicates that volume of remittances sent on average to migrants' household is of a considerable amount (Table, 3.13). Although it has been argued that volume of remittances varies from migrant to another, it is still valid that the majority of the migrant's households estimated their remittances to value more than 61 percent of the family income.

This high level of income among migrant's households provide them with some surplus resources to initiate some investments to increase their income and to diversify and reduce risks on family income.

According to Oberai and Singh (1980), remittances may raise income and consumption among the migrant's family. Actually the field survey revealed that almost 65 percent of the remittances are used to the purchasing of consumption goods to meet every day needs to support migrants' families.

The use of this high proportion of remittances to purchase consumption goods, results in a new and different pattern of consumption among the migrant's family. As large proportion of the remittances and savings are used to purchase

the durable consumer goods which provide these families with much more luxurious pattern of life. However, one can state that migration and remittances have introduced a distinct social stratification among the island community, and it is found that most of the migrant's households are relative prosperous compared to their neighbours of the non-migrants' households.

Also one can identify some different social behavior among the migrants' households in Tuti Island. For instance, among the marriage celebrations in the island one can point out that, the marriage of migrants and migrant's family member are of different nature, in the sense that, more money is spent, more items are brought by the bridegroom to his bride, ... etc.

Also it is obvious that most of the migrants' families in Tuti Island are living in beautiful houses with more attractive and comfortable services and facilities e.g. siphon, gardens, new and modern furniture, air conditions, modern decoration, ... etc.

Also the style of dresses prevailing among most of the migrants' families is different from that of the non-migrants' families. Migrants tend to provide their families, especially children, with the latest dress styles and the expensive and modern fashioned dresses.

However, the different symbols of modernization indicate that migrants' families live in a much more luxurious pattern of life.

The major question, on the other hand, is whether the change of pattern of life among migrants affects their social relation with rest of the island community.

In other words does migration create a new different social strata with new and different social behaviour prevailing the island's community?

Evidence from the field survey showed that, the migrants from Tuti Island tend to maintain and develop good social relations with their friends and relatives in the island. About 76 percent of our sample reported that they considered themselves keen to provide gifts to friends and relatives, and they spent, on average, 10 percent of their income in this item. Moreover, the majority of the sample described their vacations as an opportunity to strengthen their social ties with families and friends. Also 90 percent of the sample reported that they are keen to contribute financially to any social ceremonial celebration in their families, relatives' and friends' families. Furthermore, the noticeable contribution of migrants to the different public activities in the island, whether as individuals or collectively via their organizations, reflects that migrants are attached and linked to their community and they share their community the problems it faces.

To sum up, although migrants and their families live in a different style of life with much more luxurious and consumption pattern of life, and with more economic prosperity, still we can identify that the social ties between migrants and their families, on one hand, and the island community on the other hand are strong and sustainable. Also it is noticeable that, the economic prosperity among migrants' families does not create any social discrimination among the island community.

5.5 Ties Between Migrants and Their Community

In trying to assess the strength of ties between migrants from Tuti, their families and community, it was found that a considerable proportion of the sample reported that they come to Sudan regularly to spend their annual vacations.

Table 5.3: The Frequency of Spending Vacation in Sudan Among Migrants from Tuti Island, by Occupation, 1994

Occupation	Total No. of samples	Frequency of attending to Sudan					
		Annually		Every 2 years		More than 2 years	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Professionals	4	3	75	1	25	-	-
Officials	21	5	24	11	52	5	24
Technicians	7	-	-	4	57	3	43
Skilled labourers	7	1	14	4	57	2	29
Unskilled labourers	34	-	-	10	30	24	70
Total	73	9	12	30	41	34	47

Source: Field survey, 1994.

Table 5.3 shows that, about 12 percent of our sample survey come to Sudan annually to spend their vacations. About 41 percent of the sample come every two years to Sudan to spend their vacations among their families. The remaining (47 percent) come in an interval more than two years to Sudan. In other words, the majority of our sample, 53 percent, come to Sudan at least once every two years. This reflects that, migrants from Tuti Island tend to maintain good ties and contacts with their community. Table 5.3 shows that,

the higher the occupational status among migrant, the more frequent he comes to Sudan.

About 75 percent of the professionals and 24 percent of the officials come to Sudan annually. While only 24 percent of the officials come to Sudan during an interval of more than two years, about 70 percent of the unskilled labourers come to Sudan in an interval of more than two years (Table 5.3). This variation by occupation in the frequency of attending to Sudan may be attributed to the fact that, the higher the occupational level, the more income is expected. Consequently, the financial ability of a professional migrant to bear the financial burden of attending to Sudan (tickets, gifts, taxes, ... etc.) is more than an unskilled labourer migrant to do so.

When the migrants were asked to describe their vacations in Sudan, 33 percent of the sample described their vacations as a financial burden in terms of taxes, gifts, tickets, ... etc., but the majority (67 percent) of migrants have described their vacations as an opportunity to strengthen and enhance their social ties with families, relatives, and friends. It was also found that, about 10 percent of the sample spend their annual leave outside Sudan, mainly in Egypt and Syria.

However, the field survey revealed that, almost 90 percent of the migrants sample reported that they are keen to contribute financially to any social ceremonial celebration in their families, relatives and friends such as marriage, death, ... etc.

Another sort of ties prevailing between migrants and their community in Tuti Island, is the presents. The field survey showed that about 76 percent of the

migrant sample are quite keen to provide their relative friends with presents. It is estimated that, migrants spend, on average, 10 percent of their income in gifts to relatives and friends. Among return migrants, the percentage of income spent on gifts is estimated to be 11 percent.

When we raised a question concerning the impact of migration on family, i.e. the cost and benefit gained by family, two distinct view points were raised. One by families and the other by migrants. On the one hand, the majority of the households sample (56 percent) believe that the benefits of migration are much more than the costs. On the other hand, the majority of migrants' sample (about 67 percent) believe that migration has put some negative impacts on families. Those negative impacts or harms include the family instability, the education problems for migrant's siblings, and the weakness of the national culture and traditions inside the migrant's children.

5.6 Migrant Organizations

When assessing the contribution of migrants in supporting different public activities and utilities, it is found that about 85 percent of the migrants' sample indicated that they have contributed positively to support different activities carried out in the community. Evidence from the field survey supports this argument strongly.

However, when we discuss the issue of public activities of migrants in Tuti Island, the major point is that, migrants from the island support their community collectively. In other words, migrants from Tuti in different destinations have established their recognized benevolent societies to regulate,

organize, coordinate and channel the financial aid remitted to the island community.

Although these migrants' organizations were established as early as 1977, they were fully accepted by migrants in 1981 when a large number of migrants from Tuti at different destinations held a meeting in Tuti Island. The main objective of that meeting was to coordinate the aids remitted by migrants to the island community. The prime benefit of that meeting was that, it had managed to unify the methods, objectives and structure of these organizations at different destinations. The meeting succeeded in setting some common objectives of the migrant organizations:

1. To enhance, strengthen and support the social ties between migrants from Tuti Island in each destination;
2. to regulate, organize and coordinate all the initiatives aiming to support public activities and utilities in Tuti Island;
3. to contribute to all public activities initiated by the island community;
4. to support the poor and deprived families in Tuti Island;
5. to maintain strong ties with the island community and to keep the members of those societies in contact with their community;
6. to exchange ideas and experiences between benevolent societies of Tuti migrants at different destinations; and
7. to solve some of the problems face the members of societies at destinations (interviews).

However, these objectives were agreed upon by the different organizations at destinations. Each society has its own executive committee which is usually elected by the general assembly. The executive committee is composed of 5 -

8 persons. The major offices of these committees are the chairman, secretary-general; cultural affairs secretary; financial affairs secretary; and social affairs secretary.

After that meeting three societies were established in Saudi Arabia- in Riyadh, Jedda, and Hafer El Batin- where large number of migrants are concentrated. In United Arab Emirates also migrants from Tuti have reestablished their societies. Moreover, migrants from Tuti Island in Yemen had also established their benevolent society. Each society has its own application fees (about \$ 25 - 30) and monthly subscription for all members (range between \$ 15 - 20), and it accepts donations from members and otherwise. Besides the support of different activities in Tuti Island, these societies offer some benefits and services to their members. The major help is offered for a migrant in case of a death of a close relative, i.e. (family member). In such cases, the organization offers round tickets to the migrant and his wife to attend the funeral ceremonies in Tuti Island. In addition it provides the migrant with about \$ 300 as a contribution to the funeral ceremonies disbursement.

In the United Arab Emirates, the Tuti Migrants Organization offers more services, as it provides every visitor from Tuti Island to the UAE with \$ 300. Moreover, the UAE society provides the migrants with \$ 400 when his contract is terminated and he has to return to the Sudan. Moreover, the UAE society provides some regular support or housing allowance to groups of single migrants from Tuti "Azaba". This support is made to a house to be used as a meeting place for migrants from the island and as a reception to accommodate visitors from the island.

However, it has been noticed by the migrants themselves, that the existence of these organizations at destinations has increased the volume of migration from Tuti Island.

Massey (1993) argued that when a considerable number of migrants with certain ties such as kinship, friendship and shared area of origin, found in one destination, this may constitute what is called 'Migrant Networks'. Massey defined migrant network as the sets of interpersonal ties that connect migrants, former migrants, and non-migrants in origin and destination areas through ties of kinship, friendship and shared area of origin. (Massey, 1993: 449). The existence of these networks increases the likelihood of migration from this area of origin towards that destination. This because they lower the costs and risks of migration and increases the expected return to migration.

However, evidence from the field survey among migrants from Tuti Island indicates that the migrants organizations established at different destinations are really migrant networks. These organizations decrease the risks and costs of migration for the new migrants, and, on the other hand, increase the net expected returns to migration.

Despite the lack of the reliable statistical records concerning the money earned by these societies in the previous years and the total amount of money remitted to the island, it is still obvious that migrants from Tuti have put a noticeable positive impact on the public utilities and activities carried out in the island.

However, the annual budget of the UAE migrant organization has been estimated to be \$ 14386 during the period 1981 - 1990. From 1991 up to date

this budget, due to economic reasons, has been reduced to be around \$ 9155 annually. Also the budget of the Western district organization in Saudi Arabia is estimated to be around \$ 13329 annually, and the organization of Eastern district in Saudi Arabia, which includes Riyadh and Hafar El Batin, is estimated to be \$ 16185 annually.

So the average total annual budget of migrant organizations at Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates is estimated to be \$ 38669. It is reported that part of these budgets (up to 50 percent) is used to finance and support the activities concerning migrants at their destinations, which are held to help some migrants to solve some of their problems and strengthen social ties among migrants. The second half is being send and remitted to support public activities and utilities in Tuti Island. It is, no doubt, a big amount of money that could positively affect different aspects of life in the island. Below we discuss the contribution of migrants organizations to the public activities and utilities in Tuti Island.

5.7 Migration and Public Activities in Tuti Island

5.7.1 The Support of Mosques

Mosques in Tuti Island can be considered as one of the most important social institutions. They are the places for decision-making. There are three mosques in Tuti Island plus two under construction. The field survey showed that these mosques are the most supported institutions in the island. Table 5.4 shows that, during the period of 1984 - 1994 the mosques in the island have received donations valued to be around \$ 32912.

Table 5.4: Donations and Money Remitted by Migrants Organizations to Mosques in Tuti Island 1984 - 1994.

Year	Value (\$)	Destination source	Use made of them
1984	7677	Saudi Arabia	1225 m ² of carpet
1985	1000	Saudi Arabia	Painting of the big mosque
1986	1050	UAE	3 Water coolers
1987	1000	UAE	Purchase of fans
1987	12000	Saudi Arabia	20 Air conditions
1994	5013	Saudi Arabia	800 m ² of carpet
1994	5172	Saudi Arabia & UAE	Mosque extension-building

Source: Field survey, 1994.

Being accommodating the largest number of migrants from Tuti Island, the share of Saudi Arabia is prominent in the support of mosques in the island. Besides, another contribution to the mosques development in the island is the establishment of a new Islamic center in the island. The center now has reached an advanced stage of construction. The center will compose of some 35 rooms for different purposes. It includes a well-equipped clinic with small operation room, reading room, preschool education center, and small house for the religious leader "Imam". The total amount of money needed to complete this center is estimated to be around \$ 400000 (interview).

Moreover, mosques in Tuti have used to receive donations from individual migrants in terms of huffers, Islamic books and references, modern lamps for lighting, sound systems, ... etc.

5.7.2 The Support of Health Services Centers

The field survey revealed that migrants, through their organizations, have supported the health services in Tuti Island with both money and equipment. Table 5.5 shows some donations by migrants to the health centers in Tuti Island.

Table 5.5: Donations and Money Remitted by Migrants Organizations to the Health Sector in Tuti Island 1984 - 1994.

Year	Value (\$)	Source	Use made of remittances
1985	1500	UAE	Medical equipment
1988	4000	Saudi Arabia	Medical equipment and necessary medicines
1989	8600	UAE	Building of new clinic
1992	1200	UAE	Malaria drugs.

Source: Field survey, 1994.

The contribution of migrants to support health services in Tuti is quite remarkable. It has been reported that whenever there was some shortage of drugs and medicines, the supplies of medicines from migrants to the health center of Tuti Island is appreciated. For instance, during the floods of 1988, 1992 migrants from Tuti in UAE used to send the most needed medicines. Another contribution is the support of the migrants in UAE to build and furnish a new clinic in the island in 1989.

However, it is estimated that the total amount of money and donations remitted by migrants to support health centers in the island is about \$ 15300 during the

period 1984 - 1994. However, Table 5.5 shows that the contribution of UAE organization of Tuti migrants is more than that of the Saudi Arabia.

5.7.3 The Support of Poor Families

The support of poor and deprived families has been mentioned as one of the major objectives of the benevolent societies of migrants from Tuti Island. It has been reported that, the support of poor families has started since early 1980's. The societies in Saudi Arabia, UAE, and Yemen have used to send money to a selected committee that has a sufficient knowledge with Tuti community to identify and help the poor families and individuals.

According to this committee, it has been reported that up to 1986 the money sent by these societies used to come on regular basis, and the money distributed by the committee among the deprived families, was considered to be "sufficient". But recently and due to the irregularity of flow of remittances from the migrant organizations as well as the rapid rate of inflation, the money distributed among the poor families tends to decrease. However, the average amount of money is received monthly by the committee from the migrants organizations is only about L.s 90000. This money is to be distributed among 150 families.

However, there are still some religious seasons where donation from these organizations tend to increase e.g. Ramadan month and the different "Eed" seasons. For instance, during Ramadan of 1994 some L.s 850000 have been received by the committee and distributed among the poor families.

5.7.4 The Support of Education Institutions

The field survey revealed that education is one of the sectors that receive support from migrants. It has been reported that, the support of education from migrants is in terms of remitted money and different educational equipment, i.e. benches, chairs, tables, paintings, ... etc.

In Tuti Island most of the programs concerning education development are initiated first as a self-reliance projects, i.e. they based mainly on the resources available in the island. Among those resources, migrants' remittances occupy a unique place. Most of the projects executed in the field of education are revolving around building new classes, school rehabilitation, ... etc. In all these projects the contribution of the migrants is highly appreciated by the education leaders in the island (interviews).

However, one of the most outstanding example was the contribution made by migrants' organizations to the new secondary school for girls. In 1983/84, it has been decided that a secondary school for girls is needed in Tuti Island. The only way to achieve this project is the self-reliance approach, as the government had declared that the available resources are limited. In that project the contribution of migrants' organizations was impressive. For instance, a plot of land (about 2000 square meters) has been donated to this school by one of the migrants from Tuti in the UAE.

Moreover, it has been estimated that, the total amount of money remitted to this project is around \$ 35000. About \$ 25000 had been remitted from the UAE organization.

The contribution of migrants to support different educational projects in Tuti Island has been continuous and played a positive role to push any project towards completion.

5.7.5 The Support of Other Activities

The field survey showed that most of the youth sport teams in the island depend highly on the contribution of individual migrants who have previous membership links with that team, to provide them with the sport equipment in terms of shoes, shirts and balls.

Among the population of Tuti Island there is a group of volunteers who work to prepare the cemeteries and dig graves for the dead persons. It is found that migrants, through their organizations, remit money for this purpose frequently to help the provision of the required equipment and to feed those volunteers during their weekly camp.

Moreover, during the floods of 1988 and 1992 when a chronic shortage of medicines and drugs took place, it is reported that the contribution of migrants was effective. Ibrahim (1990), while describing the preparedness and responses to flood of 1988, stated "expatriates from Tuti, who are present in the oil-rich countries responded very positively to this appeal". The field survey showed some detailed information in this regard. The UAE society had remitted some \$ 4800 in terms of medicines and drugs. Moreover, the migrants from Tuti in Sultanate of Oman provided the island with some pump machines

to pump out the flood water, as well as pesticides to combat the prevailing epidemics.

Although the contribution of migrants in the field of transport looks like a private investment, but above all it represents one of the vital services offered to the community. Thus, when assessing the migrants' contribution to the island community, one should not neglect, but rather, should emphasize their contribution to the inland as well as river transport. Both types of transport have put a real positive impact on the transport services inside the island. The same argument can be said concerning the small-scale commercial business. As a considerable proportion of this service is owned by migrant from Tuti Island.

In 1991 a local newspaper has been issued in Tuti Island. Its objective is to support, encourage, reflect and document the socio-cultural and historical aspects of life in Tuti Island. Although this paper is not published frequently, it has got a remarkable reputation and appreciation among migrants from Tuti Island as it develops very strong ties between migrants and the island community. So migrants are used to support this paper either morally by writing to it, or financially by making some donations to cover its expenses. Actually the financial donations by migrants constitute the financial backbone to this newspaper.

5.8 Summary

This chapter examined the social impacts of migration on Tuti Island community. It is found that migration has a very positive contribution to

marriage institution by supporting the marriage ceremonial celebrations. This support of marriage increased the rate of marriage among the migrants' families. Also it is found that migrants from Tuti Island maintain a very good social ties with their local community as they provide their relatives and friends with gifts, and they regularly come to the Sudan in their vacations. Concerning social stratification, it is found that, although migration brought new pattern of life among migrants' families in terms of consumption prosperity and luxurious life, it is still valid that migrants maintain a very good stable and sustainable social relation with the island community. Also it is found that migrants from Tuti Island built their own organization to coordinate and channel their support to the island community. These organizations provide some services to the migrants themselves and to the island community. Also it is found that these migrants organizations contribute to increase the migration rate from Tuti as they reduce the costs and increase the return to migration. The field survey showed that a considerable support has directed migrants organizations towards mosques, health service centers, educational institutions, poor families, and many other public activities in the island. So it could be concluded that migration has put several positive impacts on the island's community as far as the social aspects of life are concerned.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

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The primary objective of this study was to assess the socio-economic impact of migration and remittances on Tuti Island community. It was intended that the study will investigate the impact of migration and remittances on areas such as family income, pattern of consumption, uses of remittances, rate of marriage, and support of public utilities and activities in the Island. Specifically, the study was conducted to answer the following questions:

1. What are the major socio-demographic characteristics of migrants from Tuti Island, and do these characteristics represent the local community of the Island?
2. Do remittances constitute any considerable proportion to the family income, and do they play any role in the process of income distribution and social equality and stratification in the Island?
3. Whether remittances are used in productive investment to increase family income and reduce risks on family income, or they are used for luxurious consumption?
4. What are the impacts of migration and remittances on marriage pattern and family formation in Tuti Island?

5. Whether migrants from Tuti Island contribute to the social development and public utilities support in their home community?

In order to answer the questions raised by the study, data has been collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data has been collected in a field survey using questionnaires and personal interviews. A sample of 73 migrants (15 percent of the migrants from Tuti) has been drawn based on stratified random sample, the stratification is based on education level, occupation, and destination. Another sample of 73 migrant households (15 percent of the total number of the migrant households) also has been selected for interviews. These households were intended to be the households of the migrants selected in the survey. Moreover, a sample of 47 return migrants (15 percent of the return migrants from Tuti) included in the survey. Descriptive qualitative statistical techniques such as the mean, frequency distribution, and percentage comparison, were used to analyze the data. The main findings of the study could be summarized as follows:

* The field survey revealed that the number of migrants from Tuti Island is about 484 in addition to 315 return migrants. The migrants constitute about 4.5 percent of the total population of the Island. Also they constitute about 14 percent of the labour force of the Island. It was also found that, migration in Tuti Island started during the mid 1970's and increased during 1980's, the peak period, in which migration reached its highest rate. The study found that the major receiving countries for migrants from Tuti are Saudi Arabia which accommodates some 53 percent, followed by United Arab Emirate (18 percent) and Libya about 14 percent. With regard to age structure among migrants, it is evident that migration from Tuti Island is selective in nature, as it

was found that about 65 percent of the migrants fall in the 25 - 44 age group. While this age group accommodates only 20 percent of the total population of Tuti Island. Concerning educational level among migrants from Tuti, it was found that 25 percent of the sample have got primary education; 39 percent intermediate education; 24 percent secondary education and 12 percent post-secondary education, and it is indicated that level of education among migrants is higher than that of the local population of the Island.

Concerning occupational structure among migrants before migration, it was found that the large proportion of migrants from Tuti were basically classified as employee, i.e. officials (34 percent), and about 20 percent classified as unskilled labours, and 16 percent as skilled labours. At destination, it was found that a quite noticeable mobility has taken place along the occupational scale. In other words, there is a clear trend among migrants to change or modify their jobs and career. This is done mainly to cope with the labour market circumstances at destinations.

* With regard to income, savings and remittances of migrants from Tuti Island, the study showed that there is a considerable variation concerning the volume and level of income, savings and remittances. The average annual income of migrants is found to be between \$ 3788 - 30032. The major variables that affect the level of income are the educational level, duration of migration, and type of occupation. However, the study showed that, there is a positive relation between these variables and the level of income. It was found that the average annual income of migrants with primary education is \$ 3900, secondary education is \$ 12000, and post graduate education is about \$ 22392. Also when the duration of migration is less than 4 years the years average

income is about \$ 11052, while when the duration of migration increases the migrant income increases too, e.g. the annual income of migrants with more than 15 years is about \$ 33852. Concerning the effect of occupation it was found that a professional migrant receives \$ 22392 annually, while an unskilled labour migrant receives about \$ 3660 annually. The volume of savings made by migrants ranges between 23 - 40 percent of the migrant's income. The major variables that affect the level of savings are also the same above mentioned three variables. It was also found that there is a positive relationship between these three variables and the level of savings. For instance while migrants with primary education save about 28 percent of their income, migrants with secondary education save 35 percent of their income, and graduate migrants save about 36 percent of their income. With regard to the remittances, the study found that about 88 percent of the sample sent money to their families in Tuti Island, and it was also reported that the majority of the sample remit money on regular basis. The size of remittances sent by migrants from Tuti ranges between 10 - 29 percent of the migrant's income, the same three variables (education level, duration of migration and occupation) plus the location of migrant's family constitute the major factors that affect the size of remittances. It was evident that there is a positive relationship between the above mentioned three variables and the size of remittances. Although the size of remittances increases with the level of education and occupation, it was found that the proportion of migrant's income remitted to the Island decreases with the level of education and occupation. The influence of migrant family location is of an evident importance. When the migrant family lives in Tuti Island, the size of the remitted money (25 percent of the income) is bigger than when the family lives at destination with the migrant (only 11 percent of the income).

* Concerning the impact of migration and remittances on the family income, the study revealed that a considerable proportion of the sample survey (85 percent) reported that remittances represent about 61 - 100 percent of their families income. The study argued that remittances in Tuti Island tend to increase and raise income among migrants' families as they add new financial resources to these families. Hence remittances tend to create inequality in the income distribution among the Island community, and they tend to introduce a new and different pattern of consumption among migrants' family.

According to the sample survey, about 65 percent of the remitted money is used for the provision of consumption goods to meet the daily needs of the migrants' families. Moreover, the study revealed that remittances have introduced a new social strata among the Island community, as far as the pattern of life is concerned. This argument is based on several observations such as, the level of income, the marriage ceremonial celebrations, the dresses style, the houses style, ... etc. On the other hand, the study showed that migrants and their families maintain good social relations and contacts with their local community in the Island. In other words, although migration and remittances provided the migrants and their families with a different style of social life, still they did not create any social discrimination among the Island community as far as the social interactions and relations are concerned.

* When assessing the uses made of remittances, it was found that most of these remittances are used in non-productive activities. According to the sample survey about 65 percent of the remittances used for the provision of consumption goods. Although it has been estimated that the average cost of building a house may consume the savings of four successive years, yet it was

found that 54 percent of migrants and 68 percent of the return migrants have built their own houses. Moreover, about 64 percent of the migrants' sample have reported that they have contributed to house-maintenance for their families.

Concerning the achievements accomplished by remittances, both migrants, and households have identified the construction and maintenance of houses as the first achievement. The second achievement is identified to be the improvement of the living conditions and standards of families. However, when investments are mentioned, they have been mentioned to be the fourth achievement, i.e. the last one. Also the expenses of pilgrimage and Omra for parents is one of the major areas for remittances disbursement. Almost 47 percent of the sample have contributed to this activity. Although the expenses of the religious journeys are really expensive, but they have been seen as repayment of social debts for parents and families. It was noticed that, there is a relatively high rate of land ownership among migrants and return migrants.

Actually the continuous demand by migrants has put some impacts on land use system in Tuti Island. Due to the shortage of the residential lands, agricultural lands have been transferred to residential areas. Moreover, the land prices in Tuti Island have witnessed a continuous increase due to the shortage in supply and increase in demand.

The study showed that, there is a high rate of durable consumer goods ownership. The most common goods are the electrical equipment which are owned by a large proportion of the migrants' families. This high rate of ownership of durable goods supports the argument that, most of the

remittances are spent on families welfare and luxury. However, the style of houses built by migrants indicates that a large amount of money has been spent in these houses. It is obvious, from the field survey that, the houses of migrants are of higher standards compared to non-migrant houses in the Island.

Also the study showed that migrants and return migrants have invested some of their savings in the field of services in the Island, mainly transportation and small-scale commercial business.

The high rate of ownership of the durable consumer goods, coupled with disbursement of remittances on improving living standards of the families, and huge money spent on building and maintenance of houses, all these explain why 91 percent of the families have considered their economic conditions as better as than their positions before migration.

With regard to the level of dependency of families on migrants, the field survey revealed that the level of dependency on migrants in Tuti Island community is considerable as 62 percent of the household sample reported that they depend entirely on migrants.

Concerning marriage in Tuti Island, it is argued that, there is a general tendency for lineage endogamy, and the first-cousins in Tuti Island are considered to be ideal spouses. The study revealed that, migrants from Tuti Island tend to marry their first-cousins, but with less significance, as for the Island community about 84 percent of the married persons have got married to their first-cousin, among migrants about 69 percent of the sample have got married to their first-cousins. The most interesting finding is that about 63

percent of the unmarried migrants have reported that they do not plan to marry according to *Kora* Marriage System, which represents the most accepted and traditional marriage system in the Island.

On the other hand, the field survey revealed that, the support of migrants to marriage ceremonial celebrations in Tuti Island is highly appreciated. It was found that large proportions of migrants have contributed to finance marriage of friends, relatives and family members. The contribution is of a different nature ranging from partial contribution up to the payment of all the marriage expenses. However, this contribution has put a real positive impact on marriage rate in Tuti Island. Concerning the rate of marriage in Tuti Island it was found that the rate of marriage is higher among the migrant families than non-migrant families, as the migrant families marriage ceremonies represent about 67 percent of the total number of marriage ceremonies in the Island.

* While assessing the level of the social links and ties between migrants and their Island community it was found that, migrants from Tuti Island have maintained a very strong social contacts and ties with their families and community. These social ties are maintained through the regular attendance of migrants to the Island to spend their vacations. About 57 percent of the sample survey come home to spend their vacation on regular intervals. Also they maintain good social relations through their keenness to provide their families, friends and relatives with gifts and presents. Also migrants from Tuti Island maintain their social contact through their financial contribution to the different social celebrations that take place even when they are not in the Island at the time of that celebration.

* While assessing the impact of migration on Tuti Island community, it was found that the most appropriate approach to explain migratory movement from Tuti Island is the "migration network". Where the sets of interpersonal ties, through kinship, friendship and shared community of origin, increase the likelihood of migration to occur. These migration networks lower the costs and risks of movement and they increase the expected net return to migration. All these assumptions are applicable to migrants from Tuti. The field survey showed that about 30 percent of migrants have migrated without work permit and also about 43 percent of the return migrants had migrated without work permit. The important point here is that, about 67 percent of the sample have reported that they were confident that they would be helped by their friends and relatives at destination to search for jobs. Also it was found about 76 percent of migrants from Tuti who are not accompanied by their families at destination, live among groups of migrants from Tuti, which reduces the risks and costs of migration. Moreover, it is found that about 58 percent of the sample are used to remit money to their families through the relative and friend migrants who come to spend their vacation in Tuti Island. Moreover, it is revealed from the field survey results that about 29 percent of the migrants' sample have contributed to the travel expenses of some of their friends. However, all these evidences support the argument that, migration networks have put a noticeable effect on the migration phenomenon in Tuti Island. It was also evident that, migration networks among migrants from Tuti Island are well-established organization at different destinations. These networks have been enhanced through sharing group residence-units and flats in destination, and through membership to the migrants organizations.

* At the community level, the most interesting finding concerning the support of migrants to the community activities, is that, migrants from Tuti Island tend to support and/or participate in the different activities in a very organized way. The support of migrants to their society is channeled through the migrants organizations, which were established at destinations to organize and coordinate the support of migrants from Tuti to their Island local community.

It was found that, the most supported institutions in the Island are the mosques. Migrants have supported mosques through monetary and non-monetary remittances in terms of equipment, carpets, coolers, electrical equipment, ... etc.

Also a considerable support from migrants' organizations directed to the health services in Tuti Island in terms of drugs and medical equipment for the health center. Also a new clinic was established and furnished mainly via the money remitted by migrants organizations.

All other sectors have also been supported by migrants mainly the educational sector and the youth sport and many other activities. However, all these efforts by migrants to support the different activities in the Island are highly appreciated by the Island community.

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APPENDIXES

APPENDIX No. (2)

THE IMPACT OF MIGRATION AND REMITTANCES ON TUTI ISLAND COMMUNITY

Questionnaire type (1) (for migrants)

Questionnaire No. ()

1. Socio-demographic Characteristics:

1.1 Sex: Male () Female ()

1.2 Age: 1.3 Marital status:

1.3 No. of entirely dependent persons:

1.4 No. of partially dependent persons:

1.5 Level of education:

2. Before Migration:

2.1 What was your occupation before migration?

2.2 Did you consider yourself satisfied with your job before migration?

Yes () No ()

2.3 What were the causes behind migration?

1.

2.

3.

4.

2.4 What is your destination country?

2.5 When did you migrate?

2.6 Have you migrated with a contract?

Yes () No ()

2.7 If no, please explain how did you migrate?

.....

3. Conditions During Migration:

3.1 Was your first job at destination definite?

Yes () No ()

3.2 If no, what caused you to migrate?

3.3 After how long you have managed to get a job?

3.4 Was the job suitable for your previous work experience?

3.5 What was your job in specific?

3.6 How much do you monthly paid (in \$)?

3.7 Have you acquired any new skills and experience?

Yes () No ()

3.8 Through which channel of the following do you acquire these skills?

1. Personal contact with foreigners ()

2. In service training ()

3. Overseas training ()

4. Specialized study at destination ()

3.9 Have you accompanied your family with you at your destination?

Yes () No ()

3.10 If no, do you live with migrants from Tuti island?

Yes () No ()

3.11 How much do you estimate your annual savings (in \$)?

3.12 Are you satisfied with this level of annual savings?

Yes () No ()

4. The Economic Impact of Migration:

4.1 Do you send monetary remittances? (If no, please go to question 4.13).

Yes () No ()

- 4.2 Do you remit:
1. Monthly ()
 2. Every two months ()
 3. More than two months ()
- 4.3 Do you send your remittances via:
1. Banking system ()
 2. Merchants ()
 3. Relatives and friend ()
 4. Other (specify) ()
- 4.4 Do you think that the existence of family at destination effects the volume of remittances?
- Yes () No ()
- 4.5 If you are alone at destination, how much do you send remittances per month (in \$)?
- 4.6 If you accompany your family, how much do you usually send remittances to the Sudan (in \$)?
.....
- 4.7 How much do remittances represent out of the total family income?
1. 100 - 80% ()
 2. 80 - 61% ()
 3. 60 - 41% ()
 4. 40 - 21% ()
 5. 20 - 1% ()
- 4.8 Do you usually know where these remittances are spend?
- Yes () No ()
- 4.9 If yes, please number from 1 - 7 according to the volume of money spent and specify percentage:
1. Sibling education ()
 2. Purchasing furniture ()
 3. Living expenses ()
 4. Establishing investments ()
 5. Building/maintenance of houses ()
 6. Contribution to social ceremonies ()
 7. Medical treatment ()
 8. Others (specify) ()

- 4.10 Do you intervene to identify the priorities of remittances disbursement?
 Yes () No ()
- 4.11 In addition to the remittances, have you ever contributed to any of the following family activities (please tick).
1. Marriage support ()
 2. Medical treatment abroad ()
 3. Education abroad ()
 4. Building new house for family ()
 5. Pay off-debt ()
 6. Pilgrimage and Omra for relatives ()
 7. House refurbishment ()
 8. Travel expenses for relatives ()
 9. Parents' pilgrimage ()
 10. Purchasing real-estate for relatives ()
- 4.12 From your point of view, what are the major achievements accomplished for family through the remittances?
1.
 2.
 3.
 4.
- 4.13 Have you built your own house?
 Yes () No ()
- 4.14 If yes, how much does this house cost? (in \$).

- 4.15 How do you acquire the plot of land?

- 4.16 If the answer for question 4.12 is no, have you:
1. Owned a plot of land Yes () No ()
 2. Started the building process Yes () No ()
- 4.17 How many plots of land you have got in Tuti?

- 4.18 How many plots of land you have got outside Tuti?

- 4.19 Have you owned a house outside Tuti island?
 Yes () No ()

4.20 If you have built a house can be considered as:

1. Villa ()
2. Two-floor house ()
3. Potentially two-floor ()
4. Ordinary house ()

4.21 Does your house contain any of the following?

1. House-garden ()
2. Excellent furniture ()
3. Siphon ()

4.22 What of the following items do you have?

1. TV ()
2. Cassette recorder ()
3. Video ()
4. Private car ()
5. Refrigerator ()
6. Carpet ()
7. Deep freezer ()
8. Air cooler/condition ()
9. Electric iron ()
10. Electric washing machine ()

4.23 Do you send non-monetary remittances?

Yes () No ()

4.24 If yes, what are the prominent items?

1.
2.
3.
4.

4.25 Do you consider yourself keen to provide your friends and relatives with presents and gifts?

Yes () No ()

4.26 How much do the presents and gifts constitute out of your annual income (%)?

4.27 Have you initiated any sort of income-generating activities for your family? if yes specify.

Yes () No ()

.....

4.28 Have you established any sort of large-scale investment? if yes specify.
 Yes () No ()

4.29 In comparison with the period before migration, do you believe that your family's economic condition is:

1. Far better ()
2. Better ()
3. The same ()
4. Worse ()

4.30 Is your family depending on you:

1. Entirely ()
2. Partially ()
3. Not at all ()

5. The Social Impact of Migration:

5.1 What is your principal opinion about *Kora* marriage system?

1. Strongly supportive ()
2. Supportive with preservation ()
3. Against this system ()

5.2 If you have got married, when did you get married?

1. Before migration ()
2. After migration ()

5.3 Had you got married according to the *Kora* marriage system regulations?

Yes () No ()

5.4 Is your spouse from Tuti island?

Yes () No ()

5.5 Is your spouse is a first-cousin?

Yes () No ()

5.6 If you are not married, do you plan to get married according to *Kora* marriage system?

Yes () No ()

5.7 Have you ever supported any of your friends or family members to get married?

Yes () No ()

- 5.8 What was your support? ()
1. The entire expenses ()
 2. Some sets of sheala ()
 3. Complete sets of sheala ()
 4. Some sets of sheala and partial financial support ()
 5. Partial financial support ()
- 5.9 Do you support any of your siblings in their education?
 Yes () No ()
- 5.10 Have you ever planned to continue your education and to improve your qualifications?
 Yes () No ()
- 5.11 If yes, have you already started this study programme? if yes, please specify this study programme.
 Yes () No ()
-
- 5.12 Do you consider yourself keen to spend your vacations and live with your family in Sudan?
 Yes () No ()
- 5.13 Do you come to Sudan on vacation:
 Annually () Every two years ()
 More than two years ()
- 5.14 What of the following is the most appropriate description to your vacation in Sudan?
1. An opportunity to strengthen and enhance relation with family and friends. ()
 2. It is a financial burden in terms of presents, taxes, tickets, ... etc. ()
- 5.15 Do you spend your vacation in other countries? if yes, specify these countries.
 Yes () No ()
-
- 5.16 Do you contribute to the family and friend social celebrations that take place when you are absent?
 Yes () No ()

5.17 Do you believe that migration has some social harms on your family? if yes, please specify.

Yes () No ()

5.18 Do you believe that migrants from Tuti have contributed to the socio-economic development in the island?

Yes () No ()

5.19 What are the major achievements that are executed by migrants for Tuti Island community?

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.
- 6.

5.20 How this support or contribution is being organized and channeled?

.....

With my best regards
Mohamed Salah-ELdin Mohamed
August, 1994

APPENDIX NO. (3)

THE IMPACT OF MIGRATION AND REMITTANCES ON TUTI ISLAND COMMUNITY.

Questionnaire type (2) (for household)

No:

1. The Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Family:

Rank	Sex	Age	Education	Marital status	Occupation	Annual income

1.2 How many migrants are in the family?

2. The Economic Impacts of Migration:

2.1 Does migrant send remittances to the family?

Yes () No ()

2.2 If yes, does he send remittances on:

1. Monthly ()
2. Every tow months ()
3. More than two months ()

2.3 Does he send his remittances through:

1. Banking system ()
2. Merchant ()
3. Friends and relatives ()

Do you think that the existence of the family with the migrant effects the volume of remittances?

Yes () No ()

How much does the migrant send remittances when his family stays in Sudan (in \$)?

2.6 How much does the migrant send remittances when his family accompanies with him at his destination (in \$)?
.....

2.7 How much do remittances represent out of the total family income?

1. 100 - 81 ()
2. 80 - 61 ()
3. 60 - 41 ()
4. 40 - 21 ()
5. 20 - 1 ()

2.8 Please list the major uses made of remittances (with percentage).

1.
2.
3.
4.

2.9 Does the migrant intervene to decide the uses made of the remittances?

Yes () No ()

In addition to the remittances, does the migrant contribute to any of the following items?

1. Support of marriage ceremonies ()
2. Medical treatment abroad ()
3. Education for sibling abroad ()
4. Family's house maintenance ()
5. Building a new house for the family ()

- 6. Debt pay-off ()
- 7. Parents' pilgrimage and Omra ()
- 8. Relatives' pilgrimage and Omra ()
- 9. Real-estate purchasing ()
- 10. Relatives' traveling cost ()

2.11 From your point of view, what are the major achievements accomplished to the family via remittances?

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.
- 6.

2.12 Does the migrant build his own houses?

Yes () No ()

2.13 If yes, how much does this house cost (in \$)?

.....

2.14 How did the migrant get the land plot?

.....

2.15 If the answer of 2.13 is No, has the migrant:

- 1. Owned a plot of land? ()
- 2. Started the building process? ()

2.16 How many land plots the migrant has got in Tuti island?

.....

2.17 How many plots of land the migrant has got outside Tuti island?

.....

2.18 Has the migrant got a house outside Tuti island?

Yes () No ()

2.19 If the migrant has already built a house, can it be described as:

- 1. Villa ()
- 2. Two-floor house ()
- 3. Potentially two-floor ()
- 4. Ordinary house ()

2.20 Does the house contain:

- 1. House-garden ()

2. Excellent furniture ()
3. Siphon ()
- 2.21 What of the following items is owned by the migrant: please tick
1. TV ()
2. Video ()
3. Refrigerator ()
4. Tape recorder ()
5. Air conditions ()
6. Personal car ()
7. Carpet ()
8. Washing machine ()
9. Electric fan ()
10. Electric iron ()
- 2.22 Does the migrant send non-monetary remittances?
- Yes () No ()
- 2.23 If yes, what are the prominent items?
1.
2.
3.
4.
- 2.24 Has the migrant established any sort of income-generation activities for the family? if yes, specify.
- Yes () No ()
-
- With comparison to your family's economic condition before migration, do you consider your family's economic position is:
1. Far better ()
2. Better ()
3. The same ()
4. Worse ()
- 2.26 Do you think that, your family is depending on the migrant?
1. Entirely ()
2. Partially ()
3. Not at all ()

3. The Social Impact of Migration:

3.1 Has the migrant got married?

Yes () No ()

3.2 If yes, has he got before or after migration?

.....

3.3 If he has got married after migration, had he followed the *Kora* system?

Yes () No ()

3.4 If he has not got married, do you think that the migrant will get married via *Kora* system?

Yes () No ()

Has the migrant contributed to any marriage ceremonies of the family or friends?

Yes () No ()

3.6 What was the contribution made by migrant?

.....

3.7 Does migrant attend to Sudan on his vacations:

1. Annually ()
2. Every two years ()
3. More than two years ()

3.8 Do you think that the migrant is keen to spend his vacations in Sudan?

Yes () No ()

If the migrant does not come to Sudan on vacation, does he show any keenness to contribute to any social ceremonies in the family?

Yes () No ()

3.10 Do you think that migration has any negative impacts on the family? if yes, please specify.

Yes () No ()

.....

.....

3.11 Do you think that migrant from Tuti have contributed to the public activities in Tuti island? if yes, specify.

Yes () No ()

.....
.....

With best regards
Mohamed Salah Eldin Mohamed
August 1994